

HyDelta 3

WP2a – Standalone Hydrogen Areas in the Netherlands

D2a.2 – Societal optimal hydrogen distribution

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Executive summary

Hydrogen is expected to play a key role in the Dutch energy strategy to decarbonize industries and provide balance to the renewable energy supply. Besides the national hydrogen transmission infrastructure from HyNetwork Services (HNS), hydrogen distribution grids will need to be developed to connect the HNS backbone with regional hydrogen supply and demand and to interconnect supply and demand nodes locally. Since distribution grids not only serve a large number of clients with different hydrogen pressure, purity, and volume requirements, but also can have numerous sources of hydrogen supply, the optimal grid configuration and characteristics are not immediately clear. This research provides general guidelines for future regional hydrogen grid development by reviewing the typologies of hydrogen customers that can be expected and then modelling an optimal hydrogen distribution grid that minimizes total societal costs.

In Part A, potential hydrogen customer typologies in the Netherlands are distilled from the Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (CBS) database to inform the modelling of optimal hydrogen distribution grids in Part B. Energy consumption in the form of natural gas demand per sector is used to derive analogous hydrogen demand for end-users classified as final users of energy (industrial users such as food, chemical, and paper industries, domestic transport applications, and other sectors). For each sector, the applicability of hydrogen as an alternative to natural gas is evaluated through desk research of the relevant industrial processes. Furthermore, expected hydrogen pressure and purity demands for relevant end-users, as well as the total expected annual hydrogen demand potential from the sector (PJ/year) are summarised.

The overview constructed in Part A indicates that there is a considerable theoretical demand from mobility and built environment, based on the full replacement of transport fuel or natural gas by hydrogen. Nevertheless, due to the uncertainty of the degree of hydrogen utilization in these sectors, this research focuses mostly on industrial end-users of hydrogen. Among industrial sectors, results indicate considerable demand potential in the Netherlands from the chemical, agricultural, and food & beverage industries. In reviewing the respective pressure and purity requirements of these end-users, two distinct typologies emerge: those using hydrogen for industrial heating applications, where lower pressures and purity levels are acceptable; and those using hydrogen in direct applications, e.g., as feedstock or in fuel cells, where higher purities are required, and higher pressures preferred.

In Part B, an optimization model is built using the insights gained from the review of customer typologies in Part A as well as from HyDelta 3 deliverable D2a.1 [1]. The model is constructed using the Calliope energy modelling framework [2]. The base case scenario for the model is loosely based on the H2avennet project planned in the Port of Amsterdam, which will serve numerous hydrogen off-takers (heat, feedstock, and mobility) with varying purity and pressure requirements and will have a diverse set of hydrogen supply sources (HNS backbone, imports, electrolyser, and biogasification). The model's main goal is to minimize the total system costs by making decisions on the following: optimal pipeline pressure and purity level on each transmission arc; optimal placement and capacity of purification and compression technologies; and optimal H₂ source at a given timestep. The optimized grid layout for the base case is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Optimized grid configuration for the base case. *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

The optimal grid configuration and lowest system cost are determined for the base case scenario and the robustness of the model is validated through a sensitivity analysis. Scenario analysis is undertaken to evaluate changes in the optimal grid configuration when certain key model parameters are adjusted to reflect different potential future grid characteristics and other practical considerations. Several key insights from the model are discussed in Part C and summarised below:

- **The most optimal grid configuration (lowest total system cost) from the base case involves multiple pressure and purity layers** rather than a single uniform pressure and purity specification for the entire network. This result must be considered carefully in comparison to simpler grid configurations, which are more conventional in practice based on consultation with grid operators but result in a roughly 6% increase in total system costs.
- **If the model is forced to choose a simpler grid configuration with fewer double pipelines (two pipelines on the same arc with different pressures/purities), a grid with 30 and 16 bar pipelines yields the lowest total system cost** but is less than €1 million lower than a uniformly 16 bar grid. Future hydrogen areas will need to decide whether the lower total system cost that can be achieved by having a second pressure and/or purity layer is worth the added complexities of a multi-layered grid.
- **Lower total system costs in the base case are driven by lower marginal costs of hydrogen supply from avoiding hydrogen recovery losses due to purification.** Since alternative cases with a single pressure and purity layer require a PSA to purify all low-purity imports to feed into a medium-purity grid (while the base case simply installs a separate low-purity pipeline), more hydrogen is sourced from alternative medium-quality sources with higher marginal costs (liquid H₂ and HNS imports) to compensate for the 85% recovery rate through the PSA, therefore leading to higher system costs overall. Future regional hydrogen areas with

concentrated demand and supply nodes can consider multiple pipelines to keep low and medium-purity streams separate as a lower cost alternative to large-scale purification.

- The optimal solution with multiple pressure and purity layers suggests that **end-users should be connected to a pipeline that most closely matches their required pressure and quality.** For example, heat off-takers connect to a 1 bar low-quality pipeline, feedstock to a 16 bar medium-quality pipeline, and high-pressure hydrogen supply sources exporting to the backbone (e.g., electrolyser) to a 30 bar pipeline.
- **The higher pressure and purity requirements of feedstock end-users have a significant impact on the resulting grid configuration.** A designated pipeline to keep the 16 bar medium-quality hydrogen demanded by feedstock users separate from the other low-purity low-pressure off-takers is preferred rather than selecting a low-pressure and low-purity distribution grid and installing decentralised purification and compression at each demand node. The requirements of dispersed end-users with higher pressure and purity requirements might have a stronger influence on the optimal grid configuration.
- **While multiple pressure layers and double pipelines are optimal for the concentrated H2avennet base case, it is not the case when distances between nodes increase by a factor 2 resulting in higher pipeline cost.** For less-concentrated regional hydrogen areas, fewer double pipelines and a simpler grid configuration can be expected, and the chosen grid characteristics are likely to be determined by the needs of end-users with higher pressure and purity requirements.

The results suggest that in order to meet the varying demands of potential hydrogen end-users in a distribution grid, the most optimal solution from a total system cost perspective is one involving multiple pressure and purity layers. However, under certain circumstances (e.g., a less concentrated network or more uniformity in pressure and purity demand requirements) the model chooses a simpler grid. Most importantly, grid operators must weigh the challenges associated with a complex multi-pressure layered network against the lower total system costs documented in this research when making infrastructure decisions to determine whether the most optimal configuration is still preferable when other practical considerations are taken into account.

Samenvatting

Waterstof zal naar verwachting een sleutelrol spelen in de Nederlandse energiestrategie om industrieën koolstofvrij te maken en te zorgen voor balans in de duurzame energievoorziening. Naast de nationale waterstoftransmissie-infrastructuur van HyNetwork Services (HNS) zullen waterstofdistributienetten moeten worden ontwikkeld om de transmissie-infrastructuur te verbinden met regionale vraag en aanbod van waterstof en om vraag en aanbod lokaal met elkaar te verbinden. Omdat distributienetten niet alleen een groot aantal klanten bedienen met verschillende waterstofdruk-, zuiverheids- en volume-eisen, maar ook verschillende bronnen van waterstofvoorziening kunnen hebben, zijn de optimale netwerkconfiguratie en -karakteristieken niet meteen duidelijk. Dit onderzoek biedt algemene richtlijnen voor de toekomstige ontwikkeling van waterstofnetwerken door de typologieën van waterstofklanten die kunnen worden verwacht te beoordelen en vervolgens een optimaal waterstofdistributienet te modelleren dat de totale maatschappelijke kosten minimaliseert.

In Deel A worden potentiële waterstofklanttypologieën in Nederland eerst gedestilleerd uit de database van het Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (CBS) om de modellering van optimale waterstofdistributienetten in deel B te ondersteunen. Het energieverbruik in de vorm van de aardgasvraag per sector wordt gebruikt om de analoge vraag naar waterstof af te leiden voor eindgebruikers die zijn geclassificeerd als eindgebruikers van energie (industriële gebruikers zoals voedsel-, chemische- en papierindustrie, binnenlandse transporttoepassingen en andere sectoren). Per sector wordt de toepasbaarheid van waterstof als alternatief voor aardgas geëvalueerd met behulp van literatuur onderzoek naar de relevante industriële processen. Verder worden de verwachte waterstofdruk- en zuiverheidswensen voor relevante eindgebruikers, evenals het totale verwachte jaarlijkse waterstofvraagpotentieel vanuit de sector (PJ/jaar) samengevat.

Uit het overzicht verkregen in Deel A blijkt dat er een aanzienlijke theoretische vraag bestaat vanuit de mobiliteit en de gebouwde omgeving, gebaseerd op de volledige vervanging van brandstof (transport) en aardgas (gebouwde omgeving) door waterstof. Desalniettemin richt dit onderzoek zich, vanwege de onzekerheid over de mate van waterstofbenutting in deze sectoren, vooral op industriële eindgebruikers van waterstof. Wat de industriële sectoren betreft, duiden de resultaten op een aanzienlijk vraagpotentieel in Nederland vanuit de chemische, agrarische en voedingsmiddelen- en drankenindustrie. Bij het beoordelen van de respectieve druk- en zuiverheidseisen van deze eindgebruikers komen twee verschillende typologieën naar voren: degenen die waterstof gebruiken voor industriële verwarmingstoepassingen, waar lagere drukken en zuiverheidsniveaus acceptabel zijn; en die waarbij waterstof direct wordt toegepast, bijvoorbeeld als grondstof of in een brandstofcel, waarbij hogere zuiverheden vereist zijn en hogere drukken de voorkeur hebben.

In Deel B wordt een optimalisatiemodel gebouwd op basis van de inzichten die zijn verkregen uit de beoordeling van klanttypologieën in deel A en uit HyDelta 3 deliverable D2a.1 [1]. Het model is gebouwd met behulp van het Calliope-energiemodel en het basisscenario is ruwweg gebaseerd op het H2avennet-project dat gepland is in de haven van Amsterdam, dat talrijke waterstofafnemers (warmte, grondstoffen en mobiliteit) zal bedienen met verschillende zuiverheids- en drukvereisten en zal beschikken over een diverse reeks waterstofvoorzieningsbronnen (HNS landelijk waterstofnet, import, elektrolyser en biovergassing). Het hoofddoel van het model is het minimaliseren van de totale systeemkosten door beslissingen te nemen over: optimale netdruk en -kwaliteit; optimale plaatsing en capaciteit van zuiverings- en compressietechnologieën; optimale H₂-bron op een bepaald moment. Het geoptimaliseerde netwerk voor de base case is weergegeven in Figuur 1.

Figuur 1: Geoptimaliseerde netwerk configuratie voor de base case. *lq= lage kwaliteit (98%), mq= gemiddelde kwaliteit (99.5%), hq = hoge kwaliteit (99.999%).

De optimale netwerkconfiguratie en systeemkosten, bepaald door het basisscenario van het model, worden geanalyseerd aan de hand van een reeks gevoeligheden om de robuustheid van het model te testen. Vervolgens wordt met behulp van een reeks scenario's geanalyseerd hoe de optimale configuratie verandert wanneer bepaalde parameters worden aangepast. Zo worden praktische overwegingen voor toekomstige netwerken meegenomen. Verschillende belangrijke inzichten uit de optimale netwerkconfiguratie worden verkregen en besproken in Deel C:

- **De meest optimale netwerkconfiguratie (laagste totale systeemkosten) uit het basisscenario omvat meerdere druk- en zuiverheidslagen** in plaats van één uniforme druk- en zuiverheidsspecificatie voor het hele netwerk. Dit resultaat moet zorgvuldig worden afgewogen in vergelijking met eenvoudigere netconfiguraties, die op basis van overleg met netbeheerders in de praktijk conventioneeler zijn, maar wel resulteren in een stijging van ongeveer 6% van de totale systeemkosten.
- **Als het model gedwongen wordt een eenvoudiger netwerkconfiguratie te kiezen met minder pijpleidingen, leidt een (gelaagd) netwerk van 30 en 16 bar pijpleidingen tot de laagste totale systeemkosten**, ook al zijn deze slechts €1 miljoen lager dan een uniform 16 bar netwerk. Toekomstige waterstof regio's moeten overwegen of de lagere systeemkosten die kunnen worden bereikt door een extra pijpleiding met andere druk- en/of zuiverheidsspecificaties de extra complexiteit van een dubbele pijpleiding waard zijn.
- **Lagere totale systeemkosten in het basisscenario worden veroorzaakt door lagere marginale kosten van de waterstofvoorziening door het vermijden van waterstofterugwinningsverliezen als gevolg van zuivering.** In de alternatieve scenario's met een enkele druk- en zuiverheidslaag is een PSA nodig om alle geïmporteerde H₂ met lage kwaliteit te zuiveren en in een netwerk met gemiddelde kwaliteit te voeden, terwijl in het

basisscenario een aparte lage kwaliteit pijpleiding wordt geïnstalleerd. Daarom is meer waterstof nodig voor de alternatieve scenario's om het terugwinningspercentage van 85% via de PSA te compenseren, wat in het algemeen tot hogere systeemkosten leidt. Toekomstige waterstof regio's met geconcentreerde vraag en aanbod kunnen meerdere pijpleidingen overwegen om lage en gemiddelde kwaliteit H₂ stromen gescheiden te houden als een goedkoper alternatief voor grootschalige zuivering.

- De optimale oplossing met meerdere druk- en zuiverheidslagen suggereert dat **eindgebruikers moeten worden aangesloten op een pijpleiding dat het beste aansluit bij hun vereiste druk en kwaliteit**. Warmteafnemers worden bijvoorbeeld aangesloten op een pijpleiding van lage kwaliteit van 1 bar, grondstof-eindgebruikers op een pijpleiding van gemiddelde kwaliteit van 16 bar, en waterstoftoevoerbronnen op hoge druk (zoals een elektrolyser) die naar het landelijke waterstofnetwerk exporteren op een pijpleiding van 30 bar.
- **De hogere druk- en zuiverheidseisen van eindgebruikers die waterstof gebruiken als grondstof hebben een aanzienlijke impact op de resulterende netconfiguratie**. Een aparte pijpleiding van 16 bar waterstof van gemiddelde kwaliteit voor grondstof-eindgebruikers gescheiden van de andere lage kwaliteit en lage druk waterstof afnemers heeft de voorkeur boven het selecteren van één netwerk met lage druk en lage kwaliteit omdat daarbij bij elke grondstof-eindgebruiker een compressor en zuiveringsinstallatie moet worden geïnstalleerd.
- **Hoewel meerdere druklagen en overlappende pijpleidingen optimaal zijn voor het geconcentreerde H₂avennet-basisscenario, is dit niet het geval wanneer de afstanden tussen knooppunten met een factor 2 toenemen**. Voor minder geconcentreerde waterstof regio's kunnen minder dubbele pijpleidingen en een eenvoudiger netconfiguratie worden verwacht, en zullen de gekozen netwerk-karakteristieken waarschijnlijk worden bepaald door de behoeften van eindgebruikers met hogere druk- en zuiverheidswensen.

De resultaten suggereren dat om te voldoen aan de uiteenlopende eisen van potentiële waterstofeindgebruikers in een distributienet, de meest optimale oplossing vanuit het perspectief van de totale systeemkosten een oplossing is met meerdere druk- en zuiverheidslagen. Onder bepaalde omstandigheden (bijvoorbeeld een minder geconcentreerd netwerk of meer uniformiteit in de druk-/zuiverheidseisen) kiest het model echter voor een eenvoudiger netwerk. Het allerbelangrijkste is dat netbeheerders de uitdagingen die gepaard gaan met een complex multi-druk gelaagd netwerk moeten afwegen tegen de lagere totale systeemkosten bij het nemen van infrastructuurbeslissingen wanneer andere praktische overwegingen worden meegenomen.

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1. Introduction

The Dutch government foresees a significant role for hydrogen in its energy strategy in order to achieve their climate targets of 2050. Hydrogen can play an important role towards these goals by decarbonizing industries and by providing balance to the renewable energy supply. The strategic location of the Netherlands and its existing gas infrastructure offer possibilities to accelerate the hydrogen economy, not only in the Netherlands but also in neighboring countries.

A national hydrogen transmission grid is indispensable to efficiently connect suppliers with consumers and boost the development of the hydrogen market [3]. This national hydrogen grid is planned to be developed in the coming years by HyNetwork Services (HNS), a 100% subsidiary of Gasunie. Hydrogen distribution grids need to be developed to connect the backbone to hydrogen supply or demand, but also to interconnect supply and demand locally. Areas where no backbone connection is foreseen in the nearby future, so-called standalone hydrogen areas, are also in need of distribution networks to connect supply and demand. While the characteristics of the national transmission grid are becoming increasingly clear, the characteristics of local distribution grids are still unclear.

What makes the development of distribution grids challenging, is that each grid will face a large number of potential clients, all of whom may have different demands for hydrogen in terms of volume, pressure, gas quality, demand profile, etc. The hydrogen supply can also vary amongst different distribution grids, which further increases the complexity of the problem. This research attempts to provide general guidelines for future hydrogen grid development. The principal objective of this research is to identify the characteristics of an optimal hydrogen distribution grid from the perspective of minimizing societal costs.

Several research sub-questions have been formulated to support this objective:

- What typologies of potential future hydrogen distribution grid customers can be distinguished?
- What are the needs and wishes per customer typology?
- What are determinants for the most optimal grid characteristics?

This report consists of three parts. **Part A** will provide an overview of the expected customer typologies of hydrogen users and their specifications and requirements within hydrogen distribution networks. In **Part B**, a cost optimization model is built to determine the most optimal grid configuration. In this part, the customer typologies and requirements obtained in Part A and from the interviews of HyDelta 3 deliverable D2a.1 [1] are used as inputs for the model. Finally, in **Part C**, the results of Part A and Part B are distilled in general factors, considerations and recommendations for future hydrogen distribution grids.

Part A: Customer typologies

2. Review on customer typologies

This section will provide an overview of the expected customer typologies of hydrogen users and their hydrogen specifications and requirements within hydrogen distribution networks. From a developmental standpoint, it is foreseen that future hydrogen grids – whether central or decentral – will serve a varied group of clients and users in which each of them will have different demands for hydrogen in terms of volume, handling pressure, gas quality specifications (e.g., purity), differing demand profiles, regulatory requirements, tariff structures, etc. Collectively categorizing these criteria can provide a better understanding of how these different users can be optimally served.

An overview of the different categories of energy consumers needs to be given in order to have a better understanding of the various hydrogen requirements of different users of the grid. This information is organized based on the classification defined in the “Energy balance sheet; supply and consumption, sector” database from the Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (CBS) [4] which provides annual data on the amount of energy supplied (e.g., PJ/yr) from various production sources (natural gas, renewable energy, electricity, coal etc.) and where it ends up being consumed (e.g., various industries and its constituents such as food industry, chemical industry, paper and carton etc.). The natural gas demand for each of these sectors can serve as a good starting point in order to understand their energy demand and to derive analogous hydrogen demand.

The two main sectors determined in the CBS energy balance sheet consist of the total energy sector and total final users of energy. The total energy sector is composed of extraction of crude petroleum and gas, coke-oven plants, blast furnaces, oil refineries and energy companies. Table 1 provides a more detailed definition. While these energy sector companies are generally not considered to be connected to distribution grids, but rather to transmission grids, they are still included in this typology review to ensure a complete overview of hydrogen potential. It is also important to note that the application of hydrogen within some of these categories might be irrelevant, Table 1 provides some general information on this but more details are given below.

Table 1: Definition of the total energy sector and applicability of hydrogen within a sector.

Categories within the total energy sector	Definition	Applicability of Hydrogen
Extraction of crude petroleum and gas	Installations for the extraction of crude petroleum, including natural gas liquids, and natural gas [4].	No.
Coke-oven plants	Coke ovens are large ovens within which coke, coke oven gas and coal tars are produced by high temperature carbonization of coking coal [4].	No. However hydrogen can be separated from coke oven gas [5].
Blast-furnaces	Blast furnaces are furnaces which produce blast furnace gas as a by-product when making pig iron from iron ore. During the process, carbon, mainly in the form of coke, is added to the	Yes.

	blast furnace to support and reduce the iron oxide charge and provide heat. Blast furnace gas comprises of carbon monoxide and other gases formed during the heating and reduction process [4].	
Oil refineries	Relates to manufacturing of refined petroleum products [4].	Yes, hydrogen is used extensively in oil refining activities.
Energy companies	This sector includes own use of power-generating installations and own use of other installations. This includes for example, the heating of natural gas by Gasunie Transport Services (GTS) to make it easier to get through the pipelines and consumption of electricity supplied by powerplants (if they are e.g. shut down for maintenance or lack of demand) [4].	Potentially. If for example hydrogen power plants are utilized.

The total final users of energy sector is divided into three subclassifications: industrial categories within the non-energy sector, total domestic transport applications, and other sectors. Industrial sectors considered include the manufacturing of food and beverages, textile products, paper, chemicals, building materials such as glass, ceramics, and cement, metal products, manufacturing of transport equipment (i.e., manufacturing of motor vehicles, semi-trailers, trailers etc.), construction activities and other manufacturing activities. Domestic transport refers to domestic aviation, road transport, rail transport, pipeline transport etc. The final subclassification encompasses other sectors not belonging to industry or domestic transport. This includes water supply, waste management, and waste collection and treatment, though it is unknown if hydrogen as a fuel could have any role in this category. Services is also included, which refers to the energy demand of various services and businesses (e.g., retail, transport, catering industry, financial services and education) while agriculture focuses on energy demands of greenhouses. Finally, dwellings refer to the heat demand of homes and residences. An overview of these categories is given in Table 2. The expected handling pressures and gas quality specifications will be presented in the next section.

Table 2: Overview of potential hydrogen consumer categories considered.

Main Classification	Subclassification	Further classification
Total Final Users of Energy	Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food and beverages • Textile and clothing • Paper and carton • Chemicals • Building Materials <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Glass ○ Ceramics ○ Other (e.g., cement)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic metals • Metal products and machine industry • Transport equipment • Other manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cement ○ Asphalt • Construction
	Total Domestic Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domestic aviation • Road transport • Domestic navigation
	Other Sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services • Agriculture <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Greenhouses • Dwellings

2.1 Total energy sector

Table 3 provides a categorical overview of how hydrogen is expected to be applied (type of H₂ demand), what the requirements are in terms of hydrogen purity (required quality of H₂ gas stream), the established natural gas pressure requirements from the gas pipeline network into these various sectors,¹ and what the expected pressure ranges could be for hydrogen.

Table 3: Expected type of hydrogen demand, hydrogen purity requirements, handling pressure and established network natural gas pressures for energy sector activities.

	Type of H ₂ demand (Direct/indirect)	Required Quality of H ₂ gas stream	Inlet pressure from natural gas pipeline network	Expected pressure ranges for H ₂ handling
Extraction of crude petroleum and gas	<u>Not applicable:</u> natural gas is used to power electrical equipment during upstream oil and gas production processes. IEA projects that electrification will play large role in replacing natural gas generators [6]. However, in theory it is possible to use hydrogen to power the electrical equipment, this would be indirect H ₂ demand.	<u>Not applicable:</u> It is not expected that hydrogen as a fuel will play any role in oil and gas extraction activities. Energy commodities utilized in this category consist of natural gas and electricity. In the theoretical case that hydrogen would be applied, a quality of 95% would be sufficient for combustion processes [3].	The produced natural gas is used locally and is dependent on the type of application (e.g., power generation, heating and cooling, pumps, compressors and other machinery).	Likely not applicable.
Blast furnaces	<u>Direct:</u> gas injected into blast furnace to reduce coke demand in iron ore reduction processes (900-1100°C) [7].	Blast furnace production processes do not require high purity hydrogen. The hydrogen rich mixture of gas is useful for processes such as iron ore reduction.	Natural gas is supplied to blast furnaces typically at pressures ranging from 2 to 7 bar. When	Hydrogen is supplied to blast furnaces at moderate to high pressures. Typical supply pressures

¹ Note that this is dependent on the type of industrial appliance used.

			injecting natural gas into the blast furnace for combustion, the pressure ranges from 0.5 to 2 bar [8].	range from 5 to 70 bar. Injection pressures generally range from 1 to 10 bar [9].
Oil refineries	<u>Direct and indirect.</u> <u>Indirect:</u> oil is heated in gas-fired furnace (100-600°C). <u>Direct:</u> if used for refining during hydrocracking or hydrotreating processes.	For indirect heating lower quality of hydrogen is acceptable but high-quality hydrogen (99.9% purity) is required if used for refining [10].	Highly dependent on the type of application. E.g., for hydrotreating the pressure ranges fall between 7-50 bar for feeds with a boiling point up to 350°C [11]. Higher pressures above 150 bar can also be utilized [12].	Not expected to be drastically different in relation to established methods and parameters.
Energy companies	<u>Indirect:</u> on-site heat and power generation for daily operations	95% is sufficient for combustion processes [3].	Highly dependent on the type of activity (4-8 bar to 30-40 bar).	Highly dependent on the type of activity (4-8 bar to 30-40 bar).

Table 4, Table 6 and Table 10 provide the total natural gas demand of the aforementioned sectors in PJ/y. The volumetric energy equivalent for both natural gas and hydrogen has been provided in Mm³/yr and a mass equivalent has been provided as well in metric ktonne/yr.

Details regarding the conversions for the aforementioned tables are as follows:

1PJ of energy is equivalent to 31,600,000 normal cubic meters (Nm³) of low calorific natural gas² [13]. The heating value of hydrogen is used in order to derive the hydrogen volumetric equivalent of 1PJ. Here we opt for the lower-heating-value³ (LHV) of hydrogen which is 10.78 MJ/Nm³:

$$1PJ \times \frac{1Nm^3H_2}{10.78 MJ} \times \frac{10^9MJ}{1PJ} \approx 92,764,378 Nm^3H_2$$

Hence 31,600,000 Nm³ of natural gas is roughly equal to 92,764,378 Nm³ of hydrogen. Essentially, for the same amount of energy (here 1PJ) hydrogen occupies ≈3 times⁴ more volume compared to natural gas which underlines the higher compression energy requirements for storing/transporting hydrogen.

The mass equivalent can be found by using the density of hydrogen at NTP⁵ conditions which is 0.0838 kg/m³:

² Based on the low calorific value of natural gas. CV = Energy content (MJ)/Volume (m³) = 10⁹MJ/31.6Mm³ = 31.64MJ/m³ which is in the range of low calorific value gas: 33 – 37 MJ/m³.

³ It was decided to use the LHV of hydrogen since in most practical applications, such as home heating or industrial processes, the water vapor remains in its gaseous form as it is released into the atmosphere without condensing back into liquid.

⁴ This value would be ≈2.5 times if the HHV of hydrogen was used.

⁵ NTP, or normal temperature and pressure is defined as a temperature of 20 °C (293.15 K) and a pressure of 1atm (101.325 kPa)

$$92,764,378 \text{ Nm}^3 \text{ H}_2 \times \frac{0.0838 \text{ kg H}_2}{1 \text{ Nm}^3 \text{ H}_2} \approx 7,773,655 \text{ kg H}_2 \approx 7.77 \text{ kton H}_2$$

Table 4: Total natural gas and equivalent hydrogen demand volumes for the energy sector.

	Number of locations	Total NG demand (PJ/y)	Total NG demand (MNm ³ /y)	Total H ₂ demand (MNm ³ /y)	Total H ₂ demand (kt/y)
Extraction of crude petroleum and gas	261 (oil and gas production sites operational or planning to be by 2025)	17	547	-	-
Blast furnaces	1 (2 furnaces - Tata IJmuiden)	1	16	46	4
Oil refineries	6 (Rotterdam and Vlissingen)	21	651	1911	160
Energy companies	Unknown	236	7454	21883	1834

2.2 Industry

Table 5 refers to expected applications of hydrogen within various industrial categories. Expected pressure handling ranges for hydrogen are approximations. The feed-in pressure of the natural gas pipeline network for a majority of the industries in Table 5 is between 4-8 bars⁶.

Table 5: Expected type of hydrogen demand, hydrogen purity requirements, handling pressure and established network natural gas pressures for industries.

	Type of H ₂ demand (direct/indirect) [14]	Required quality of H ₂ gas stream	Expected pressure ranges for H ₂ handling
Food & beverages	<p>Hot water/steam generation: indirect (0-100°C),</p> <p>Drying: indirect (100-200°C),</p> <p>Chemical conversions: indirect/direct (100-600°C),</p> <p>Distillation: indirect (100-600°C).</p>	<p>The quality will depend on the type of application. For indirect applications lower quality is sufficient but for direct applications (e.g., roasting coffee) specific purity demands may be needed.</p>	<p>Hydrogen supply pressure via pipeline is expected to be 4-8 bar.</p> <p><i>Operating pressure of:</i></p> <p>Boiler: For small to medium-sized boilers used in food processing and cooking applications, typical natural gas operating pressures range from 2 to 5 bar. Larger boilers operate anywhere between a natural gas pressure from 5 to 20 bars. It's expected that in general boilers utilizing hydrogen would have a range between 5-30 bars [15].</p> <p>Drying: Highly dependent on the drying equipment and the type of application, approximately 1-6 bars [16].</p> <p>Chemical Conversion: Highly dependent on application e.g. 1-5 bar for low-pressure</p>

⁶ The only exception is for manufacturing of transport equipment which is <8 bars, other types of manufacturing processes <8 bars, and the category of construction where the utilization of hydrogen for construction purposes is not expected.

			hydrogenation, 20-60 bar for high-pressure hydrogenation, 10-30 bar for amino acid production, 1-3 bar for high-fructose corn syrup [17].
Textile & clothing	Hot water/steam generation: indirect (0-100°C), Drying: indirect (100-200°C).	Only indirect heating so quality is of lower importance.	Hydrogen supply pressure via pipeline is expected to be 4-8 bar. <i>Operating pressure of:</i> <i>Boiler:</i> 5-30 bar [15]. Boilers are significantly used in the textile industry for generating steam which is used in dyeing, bleaching, printing processes [18]. <i>Drying:</i> 1-1.5 bar. Highly dependent on the type of application but most applications should be around atmospheric pressure.
Paper and carton	Hot water/steam generation: indirect (0-100°C), Drying: indirect (100-200°C).	Only indirect heating so quality is of lower importance.	Hydrogen supply pressure via pipeline is expected to be 4-8 bar. However, for the time-being the paper and carton industry in the Netherlands will depend on electrification to decarbonize [19]. <i>Operating pressure of:</i> <i>Boiler:</i> Operating pressure of boilers in the paper industry is highly dependent on the type of boiler. E.g., water tube boilers need 30-100 bar, fire tube boilers 10-25 bar etc [20]. An equivalent hydrogen boiler should be able to provide the same level of pressure requirements. <i>Drying:</i> typically steam drums are used that dry pulp to paper. Electric or gas infrared heaters and convection heating hoods are also used [21]. Convection heating hoods relying on combustion from hydrogen can play a role [22].
Chemicals	Feedstock: direct (variable temperatures), Drying: indirect (100-600°C), Chemical conversions: indirect (100-600°C), Distillation: indirect (100-600°C).	For indirect heating quality is of lower importance. For feedstock, high quality is often desired (>99%) to prevent undesired side reactions.	Hydrogen supply pressure via pipeline is expected to be 4-8 bar. Utilization pressure of hydrogen is highly dependent on the type of application and can span a wide range. Lower pressures are expected for indirect usage but may be very high as well (e.g., 200 bar for Haber-Bosch process).
Glass	Melting: direct (1200-1650°C), Annealing: direct (200-900°C).	Flue gas composition is important for product quality and heat transfer. Thus,	Hydrogen supply pressure via pipeline is expected to be 4-8 bar.

		low variation in H ₂ stream composition and knowledge of impurities is important.	Combustion chamber pressure is expected to be around atmospheric pressure or slightly higher depending on the type of furnace used.
Ceramics	Baking: direct (1000-1200°C), Drying: indirect (<100°C).	Hydrogen quality will have a direct influence on product properties such as color and hardness. Hence, it's vital that there are little variations in quality.	Hydrogen supply pressure via pipeline is expected to be 4-8 bar. Combustion chamber pressure of the kiln is usually close to atmospheric pressure or slightly above: 1-1.5 bar.
Other (e.g. cement and asphalt)	Heating (Cement): direct and indirect (1800 - 2200°C). Heating (Asphalt): indirect (hot mix asphalt 120 – 190°C) (warm mix asphalt 100 – 150 °C) (half-warm asphalt 70-100 °C).	For clinker production hydrogen could have an impact on cement quality. Addition of hydrogen can improve the combustion characteristics [23].	Hydrogen supply pressure via pipeline is expected to be 4-8 bar. Hydrogen can be utilized in the cement industry as fuel for cement kilns [24]. Kiln injection pressure is expected to be around atmospheric pressure. For asphalt production heat is applied to the asphalt mixture in a rotary drum dryer [25].
Basic metals	Melting: direct (up to 2000°C), Annealing: direct (200-900°C).	For steel hardening, the interaction between the product and the flue gas affects its properties. Thus, purity of the gas stream is very important.	Hydrogen supply pressure via pipeline is expected to be 4-8 bar. Utilization pressure depends on the type of furnace. Induction furnaces will operate around atmospheric pressure while vacuum induction furnaces operate under vacuum conditions. Blast furnaces normally operate pressure ranges between 2 to 5 bar. Any hydrogen fired furnace should also be required to operate at similar pressure ranges.
Metal products and machine industry	Annealing: direct (200-900°C), Heating: direct/indirect (1800 - 2200°C for ferrous metals), Heating: direct (500 - 1500°C for non-ferrous) e.g., copper, aluminium, tin, zinc, etc. in smelting furnaces with flue gases.	Temperature, radiation and flue gas composition are important for product quality and heat transfer.	Same as basic metals.
Manufacturing of Transport equipment	Direct: natural gas-fired heaters used to directly heat conditioned air used in paint drying process (80% of gas use); Remaining natural gas is used for heating buildings [26].	Unknown if hydrogen would be utilized in the manufacturing process of automobiles.	Unknown.

Other manufacturing	<i>Indirect:</i> gas-fired oven for drying powder coating on furniture manufacturers.	Only indirect heating so quality is of lower importance.	Depends on the type of activity.
Construction	<i>Direct:</i> hydrogen fuel cells for construction vehicles or hydrogen generators for construction sites.	Assumed >99.97% H ₂ purity required since fuel cells are utilized	Potentially not applicable.

Table 6 provides the total natural gas demand in both PJ/y and Mm³/y for 2022 for various industrial categories. The equivalent of these demands in terms of hydrogen has also been calculated using the conversions explained in section 2.1.

Table 6: Total natural gas and equivalent hydrogen demand volumes for various industrial categories.

Industry	Number of locations	Total NG demand (PJ/y)	Total NG demand (MNm ³ /y)	Total H ₂ demand (MNm ³ /y)	Total H ₂ demand (kt/y)
Food & beverages	>500 (50 ETS-locations)	61	1918	5631	472
Textile & clothing	Unknown	2	73	213	18
Paper and carton	21	16	499	1466	123
Chemicals	390	172	5448	15993	1340
Building materials		19	588	-	-
Glass	6	7	209	612	51
Ceramics	40	7	231	677	57
Other (e.g. cement)	Unknown	5	149	436	37
Other (e.g. asphalt ⁷)	34	1 – 2	44 – 66	130 - 195	11 – 16
Basic metals	400	11	348	1020	86
Metal products and machine industry	Unknown	8	253	742	62
Transport equipment	1 (VDL Nedcar)	2	54	158	13
Other manufacturing	Unknown	1	28	83	7
Construction	Unknown	3	82	241	20

2.3 Domestic transport

The potential application of hydrogen in the mobility sector is a well-established fact: the use of hydrogen as fuel in vehicles can play an important role in decarbonising the transport sector and achieving net-zero emissions targets [27]. The growth of hydrogen refuelling stations worldwide has been slow and steady but has followed an upward trend. As an example, in 2015 there were approximately 300 public hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) in the world [28]. By the end of 2022, 814 hydrogen refuelling stations were operational worldwide [29].

The decades of experience that has been gained through numerous demonstration projects for hydrogen refuelling stations has resulted in the development of global standards and functional specifications such as the 350/700-bar fuelling protocols which have developed under the ISO/TC 197

⁷ The data here is based on 2020 values and depicts a range. Asphalt production requires anywhere between 6.12 – 9.41 m³ of natural gas per ton of asphalt [25].

standards [30]. The ISO TC 197 is the most active in the HRS field since it focuses on hydrogen fuel stations and hydrogen-powered vehicles. The ISO TC 197 standards provide specifications and guidelines for the design, construction, operation, and maintenance of hydrogen fuelling stations, as well as the performance and safety requirements for hydrogen fuel cell vehicles [31]. The main standard associated with general and specific requirements for the design and operation of HRSs is the ISO 19880 (1-9) standard which provides guidance for safe and efficient hydrogen refuelling, ensuring compatibility between various refuelling stations and vehicles, and provides a framework for commercial operations [31]. Among these, the ISO 19880.5 standard suggests the requirements of dispensers for hydrogen dispensing at 70 MPa (or 700 bar) with a temperature between -40 °C and 65 °C [32].

The SAE J2601-2 suggested ~20-30kg of hydrogen refuelling into heavy-duty vehicles within 5-10 min [27], this protocol was developed with dispensing hydrogen into heavy-duty vehicles which rely on 350 bar dispensers. This protocol suggested a maximum hydrogen flow rate of 7.2 kg/min with an ambient temperature between -40 °C and 50 °C.

Table 7 provides more details on the type of demand needed for this sector and the expected quality streams.

Table 7: Expected type of hydrogen demand, hydrogen purity requirements, and handling pressure for transport applications of hydrogen.

	Type of H ₂ demand (direct/indirect)	Required quality of H ₂ gas stream	Feed-in Natural Gas Pipeline Network	Expected pressure ranges for H ₂ handling
Domestic aviation	Currently not applicable but applications could exist beyond 2035/2040.	Expected to be >99.97%.	Not applicable.	Undetermined at this point.
Road transport	Direct: Transportation via FCEV's. Also possible are dual fuel engines (Diesel+H ₂) (see [33]).	>99.97% H ₂ purity required.	Not applicable.	350/700 bar hydrogen dispensers are utilized.
Rail transport	Direct: Hydrogen can be a means of locomotion for trains via fuel cells.	>99.97% H ₂ purity required.	Not applicable.	350/700 bar hydrogen dispensers are utilized.
Domestic navigation	Direct: Inland barges running on fuel cells.	Assumed >99.97% H ₂ purity required since fuel cells are utilized.	Not applicable.	Refuelling of barges is done by swapping empty hydrogen cannisters with pressurized cannisters at special terminals.

Table 8 provides values on the final consumption of petroleum products for road, rail, maritime, and aviation categories in millions of kilograms of fuel for 2022 [34].

Table 8: Total fuel demand for road, rail, maritime and aviation in kt/yr.

Final consumption transport sector	Petrol consumption (kt)	Diesel consumption (kt)	LPG consumption (kt)	Marine diesel consumption (kt)	Kerosene type jet fuel (kt)	Aviation gasoline (kt)	Total (kt)
Road transport	3928	4404	115	-	-	-	8447
Rail transport	-	21	-	-	-	-	21
Domestic navigation	-	-	-	245	-	-	245
Domestic aviation	-	-	-	-	9	1	10

Calculating the equivalent hydrogen needs for these different mobility applications is highly dependent on a series of assumptions such as what kind of motor vehicle is considered (e.g., diesel bus, diesel truck, diesel car, petrol car) since each has their own different fuel consumption rates. Detailed information is also needed on the share of various fleets (buses, trucks, passenger cars) that utilize a specific fuel category. Then, in order to derive conversions, there are also differing values for the level of consumption for fuel cell electric trucks, buses and vehicles. Based on a multitude of assumptions that needs to be made and the fact that this type of calculation falls outside the scope of this study, it has been decided to omit providing equivalent hydrogen needs for mobility applications.

2.4 Other sectors

The energy requirements of several other sectors are also of interest, such as the services industry, the agricultural sector, and dwellings; this information is shown in Table 9 and Table 10. Services refers to the energy requirements of wholesale and retail trade, transportation and storage, accommodation and food serving, financial institutions, etc. It is expected that for this sector, a majority of energy needs will relate to heating hence utilization of hydrogen in gas boilers could be a possibility. Another significant category is the agricultural sector. The potential application of hydrogen in this sector can be broad and wide, ranging from utilizing hydrogen as a fuel for farming equipment all the way to fulfilling the energy requirements of greenhouses. The consumption of natural gas as a whole for the agricultural industry in the Netherlands stands at 95.0 PJ/yr based on 2023 data.

Dwellings is another important sector and refers to usage of energy in private, non-commercial applications and excludes transport. The potential application of hydrogen within the built environment is still debated and it is not clear whether it will have a significant role in supplying heat to the built environment. In HyDelta 3 D2a.1 [1] the viability and potential of standalone hydrogen areas is discussed based on its end-users. A standalone hydrogen area with built environment end-users alone was deemed likely not viable. However, there may be potential for hydrogen in built environment in areas connected to the backbone or where ammonia can be cracked locally. Electrification, e.g., the utilization of heat pumps and hybrid heat pumps (using biomethane or possibly hydrogen) will most likely play a more dominant role in providing heat for dwellings. Nonetheless, the hydrogen equivalent of natural gas consumption in dwellings has been included in the table below only to provide an understanding of what the volumetric equivalent would be in terms of hydrogen.

Table 9: Expected type of hydrogen demand, hydrogen purity requirements, handling pressure and established network natural gas pressures for services industries, agriculture and dwellings categories.

	Type of H ₂ demand (direct/indirect)	Required quality of H ₂ gas stream	Feed-in Natural Gas Pipeline Network	Expected pressure ranges for H ₂ handling
G-S, U Services	<i>Indirect</i> : natural gas likely used for heating in majority of businesses included in these industries (most buildings in NL use natural gas boilers for heating) [35].	98% purity for pure hydrogen boilers (Type I Grade A) [36]. Existing residential boilers upgraded for hydrogen usage could handle up to 20% blends of hydrogen in H ₂ :NG blends.	<1 bar(g)	Expected <1 bar(g)
Agriculture	<i>Direct/Indirect</i> : depends on the type of application.	Depends on the application but could be utilized for mechanized farm equipment, tractors etc.	-	Dependent on the activity
Crop Cultivation (including greenhouse agriculture)	<i>Direct</i> : combustion of hydrogen in CHP gas engines OR use of hydrogen in peak boilers; <i>Indirect</i> : purchase of residual heat from large-scale electrolyzers [37].	99.9% purity recommended for industrial fuel for heat and power generation [36]. 95% is sufficient for combustion processes.	Unknown	Unknown
Dwellings	<i>Indirect</i> : For residential and district heating purposes.	98% purity for pure hydrogen boilers (Type I Grade A) [36]. Existing residential boilers upgraded for hydrogen usage could handle up to 20% blends of hydrogen in H ₂ :NG blends.	0.03 - 0.1 bar(g)	Low pressure

Table 10: Expected type of hydrogen demand, hydrogen purity requirements, handling pressure for services industries, agriculture and dwellings categories.

	Total NG demand (PJ/y)	Total NG demand (MNm ³ /y)	Total H ₂ demand (MNm ³ /y)	Total H ₂ demand (kt/y)
G-S, U Services	95	2993	8785	736
Agriculture	95	3002	8813	739
Crop Cultivation (including greenhouse agriculture)	94	2980	8748	733
Dwellings	237	7502	22022	1845

Part B: Modelling of regional H₂ area

3. Methodology

In order to determine what a hydrogen distribution grid could look like based on the lowest societal costs, a modelling approach was adopted in which the total system costs are minimized. The model was built using Calliope, a free and open-source tool to build energy system models. A base case model was built, loosely based on the H2avennet project, which contains several different types of hydrogen suppliers and end-users. On this base case, a sensitivity analysis was performed which provided additional insights in the effect of the grid lay-out, the compression and purification costs, pipeline costs, and increased mobility demand. Several alternative scenarios were also investigated in order to further assess the model’s relevance to future regional hydrogen grids and distil general insights.

3.1 Interviews

HyDelta 3 D2a.1 describes the role of standalone hydrogen areas in the successful roll-out of the hydrogen infrastructure in the Netherlands [1]. In this deliverable, a case study approach with 20 semi-structured interviews was applied to investigate the research question. An overview of the relevant information regarding the pressure and quality requirements obtained during these interviews is given in Table 11. This information is used as input for deciding the transmission technology options and the pressure and quality requirements for different demands.

Decisions based on input information:

- Option for truck or high-pressure pipeline for mobility end-users
- Other pressures in pipelines: 4, 8, 16 bar
- Quality options: low quality = 98% (HyNetwork Services (HNS) backbone); medium quality = 99.5%; high quality = 99.999%
- High pressure and high-quality demand for mobility⁸: 99.999%, 700 bar
- Low pressure and low-quality demand for heating (houses + industry): 98%, 1 bar
- Medium pressure for feedstock: 99.5%

Table 11: Overview of pressure and quality requirements for 9 diverse standalone hydrogen areas in the Netherlands.

Project	Pressure in grid ^d (bar)	Planned end-user (short term)	Pressure at end-user (bar)	Quality required from end-user
Bolsward	3	Industrial burners	0.003	95% ^a
H2GO	8	Heating houses	0.003	95% ^a
H2avennet	16	Industry	Varies	Varies ^b
GROHW	16	Industrial/Mobility	Varies	>99.9%
Duwaal	40	Mobility	350 to 700	>99.9%
Agriport A7	Adapt to backbone	CHP	-	99%
H2 Hollandia	- ^c	Likely mobility	350 to 700	>99.9%
Zephyros	- ^c	Mobility	350 to 700	>99.9%
Hessenpoort	- ^c	Mobility	350 to 700	>99.9%

^a Not specified in interview, but 95% is typically sufficient for combustion processes. ^b There are various off-takers foreseen and the required hydrogen quality varies from relatively low (95%) for combustion purposes to high (>99.9) for feedstock applications. ^c No H₂ grid planned for short term, transport is foreseen with tube-trailers. Pressure in tube-trailers for H2 Hollandia will be 500 bar, for the other projects it is not specified. ^d Maximum pressure but does not account for expected pressure drop (e.g., end-users in the H2avennet grid are guaranteed a minimum of 8 and maximum of 16 bar).

⁸ Mobility here refers to passenger vehicles i.e. cars, not buses/trucks.

3.2 Modelling

The main aim of the model is to configure a hydrogen grid (containing pipelines/trucks, compressors and purification technologies) with the lowest costs that will satisfy all different customer demands at all times. The model is constructed in Calliope, an open-source energy system modelling tool maintained and developed on GitHub [38], designed for planning future energy system configurations based on high resolution temporal data (e.g., electricity prices, wind profiles, and industrial off-taker demand profiles) and varying constraints (e.g., costs and capacities of pipelines, compressors, and purification technologies) [38] [2].

In this work, Calliope (v0.6.10) is used to build a model hydrogen distribution network and optimize it in such a way that the total societal costs of such a system are minimized. The pipeline network chosen for the base case of the model is loosely based on the H2avennet project (for layout see below) planned in the Port of Amsterdam, which will serve numerous hydrogen off-takers with varying purity and pressure requirements (heat, feedstock, and mobility) and will have a diverse set of hydrogen supply sources (HNS backbone, imports, electrolyser, and biogasification) [1]. The model’s main goal is to minimize the objective function (system lifetime costs) based on a series of decision variables described in section 3.2.2. The general scope and principal assumptions are outlined in Table 12.

Table 12: Assumptions and scope of model.

Assumptions
All H ₂ values are converted to MW using LHV H ₂ (33.33 kWh/kg)
All distances are specified in km
Continuous supply available from backbone and import terminals
Fixed layout (based on H2avennet network) of supply/demand nodes and transmission arcs
Assumed maximum 40% pressure drop for 4, 8, and 16 bar pipelines; maximum 5% for 30 bar pipelines (see 3.2.5 for additional explanation of the assumed pressure drop and how it is taken into account in the pipeline section)
Outside of Scope
Admixing or blending with natural gas (demand must be met with hydrogen alone)
Hydrogen storage within the distribution system

3.2.1 Assumed grid layout

The base case for the model is based on the H2avennet project. A schematic overview of the assumed layout of all locations for the base case is given in Figure 2. The locations for the base case are based on a fictionalised scenario of how the supply and demand nodes of the H2avennet network could be arranged within the Port of Amsterdam, obtained by consulting experts involved with the project. The arc distances used to connect individual nodes reflect the straightened pipeline distance that is expected between supply and demand locations and the total pipeline length of the network should closely reflect reality.⁹

⁹ See *HyDelta 3 D4b.1 – Controlling protocols and strategies for decentralized hydrogen feed-in*, which uses the same layout and scenario for analysis.

Figure 2: Overview of the assumed layout of the H2avennet base case.

3.2.2 Objective function and decision variables

The objective of the model is to minimize the total system costs. The objective function for the model is given in eqn. (1):

$$\min : z = \sum_{loc::techs} cost_{loc::tech} \quad (1)$$

in which the minimum costs are determined by the sum of the costs for each set of locations and technologies (loc::tech). For example, $loc_{X1}::tech_{compressor}$ denotes a compressor installed at location X1.

Costs for each loc::tech are calculated by annualising all investment costs and summing them with the annual fixed and variable operational costs using eqn. (2):

$$cost_{loc::tech} = cost_{annualised_capex} + cost_{annual_opex} + \sum_{timesteps} cost_{variable_opex} \quad (2)$$

$$cost_{annualised_capex} = depreciation_rate \times cost_{capex} \quad (3)$$

$$depreciation_rate = \frac{interest_rate(1 + interest_rate)^{lifetime}}{(1 + interest_rate)^{lifetime} - 1} \quad (4)$$

where $cost_{annualised_capex}$ is given by eqn. (3) and $depreciation_rate$ is given by eqn. (4). All remaining mathematical calculations can be found in the Calliope documentation [39].

A summary of the decision variables and their capacity ranges is given in Table 13. A summary of the fixed technologies and their capacities is given in Table 14.

Table 13: Decision variables used in the Calliope model.

Decision variables	Options given
Transmission technology (pipeline vs truck) at each arc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4, 8, 16, or 30 bar pipeline with 98%, 99.5%, or 99.999% purity 350 bar tube trailer truck with 98%, 99.5%, or 99.999% purity (operating only between hydrogen refueling station (HRS) node and electrolyser)
Decide capacities & placement of compressors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity: min = 0 MW, max = 400 MW 1 to 4 bar 4 to 8 bar 8 to 16 bar 16 to 30 bar 30 to 350 bar (only at HRS node) 350 to 700 bar (only at HRS node)
Decide capacities & placement of purification technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pressure swing adsorption (PSA): capacity 70-833 MW (purify to 99.999%) Polymeric membranes: capacity 3-233 MW (purify to 99.5%)
Decide optimal H ₂ source at a given timestep	HNS backbone; LOHC import; liquid H ₂ import; electrolyser; biomass gasification; alternative HRS supply.

Table 14: Summary of technologies with fixed locations and capacities in the model.

Technologies with fixed locations and capacities (see Figure 2)
HNS backbone (200 MW _{H2})
LOHC import (100 MW _{H2})
Liquid H ₂ import (75 MW _{H2})
Electrolyser (200 MW _{H2} peak production)
Biomass gasification (7.4 MW _{H2} peak production)
Alternative HRS supply via truck (fixed location but model can decide whether to install it or not) (supply profile matches HRS demand profile)

3.2.3 Constraints

The Calliope energy model provides a framework for building upon typical energy model constraints with user-defined custom constraints. For instance, by default the model employs an energy balance constraint, which requires that the production and consumption of energy carriers in the system are balanced across all locations. From a practical standpoint, ensuring balance between supply and demand in such small networks is particularly challenging and will likely require dynamic pressure

management utilising real-time data to adjust pressure and flows using digitized equipment.¹⁰ Other balancing techniques could include surface storage, linepacking enabled by large pressure ranges, or curtailment of variable supply sources such as the electrolyser.

However, given the limitations imposed by the relatively simplistic Calliope model, practical balancing strategies such as linepacking are not considered. Instead, we assume that balancing can be done on an hourly basis by 1) adjusting import flows from LOHC, LH₂, and backbone imports; 2) curtailing biomass production; 3) exporting excess hydrogen production in the system to the HNS backbone. In reality, additional investments in digitization and pressure control would be required, but for simplicity, this is assumed to be inherently possible within the modelled system.

Additionally, user-defined constraints are added to specify the bounds of the base case energy system. Table 15 lists general custom constraints added to the model for the base case scenario. See section 3.2.5 for all techno-economic constraints specific to each technology (e.g., compressors, pipelines, electrolyser, etc.). For the mathematical formulation of the model and all remaining default constraints, please refer to the Calliope documentation [39].

Table 15: General user-defined constraints used for base case model.

Constraint	Description
Demand must be met	Force model to meet all demand and return infeasibility error if demand cannot be met by available supply
Force electrolyser operation	Forces electrolyser to operate based on available wind resource rather than market price
Force backbone export	Requires all excess hydrogen supply to be exported to the backbone
Constant supply from backbone and imports	Assumes that specified maximum capacities for backbone and imports are available at all timesteps
No spatial restrictions for installed technologies	Assumes that there are no spatial constraints for placing multiple technologies (e.g., compressors or pipelines) on any given node or arc.
Negligible losses from H ₂ leakage during transmission	Assumes that transmission arcs (pipelines and trucks) have negligible hydrogen losses during transport due to leakages
Negligible costs of decompression ¹¹	Assumes that costs of depressurizing incoming hydrogen streams to meet lower pressure demand are negligible
Interest rate and inflation	System lifetime costs are calculated assuming an interest rate of 2% and all investments costs are corrected for inflation to 2024 [40] (assuming investments will be taken in the near term), while market electricity prices are projected for 2030 [41] to reflect the long-term operation of the system more accurately

¹⁰ See *HyDelta 3 D4b.1 – Controlling protocols and strategies for decentralized hydrogen feed-in* for further discussion of balancing considerations for the H2avennet case.

¹¹ For practical reasons, the model assumes a cost of €1 per MW of installed “decompression” or “depurification” capacity that is required to ensure feasibility of the model. Decompression, for example, could represent a 4 bar hydrogen supply being “converted” to 1 bar hydrogen to satisfy heat demand (which needs only 1 bar). Depurification, for example, could represent medium-quality hydrogen being “depurified” to low-quality to satisfy heat demand (which needs only low-quality). Although depurification is a fictional process, it allows the model to keep higher-purity streams of hydrogen separate from low-purity streams. The €1 per MW costs are meant to be small enough to not impact the overall system costs but simultaneously prevent the model from deciding to install these fictional technologies at every node, which would happen if their costs had instead been set to €0 per MW.

3.2.4 Solving the problem mathematically

Calliope uses Pyomo as a backend interface to connect with commercial solvers (in this case, Gurobi) to perform efficient optimization of complex mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) models. The model is solved using the Gurobi optimizer (v.11.0.1) on an Apple M1 CPU with 8 logical processors (8GB RAM). Due to the complexity of the problem, improving solution time to allow for analysis of multiple alternative scenarios is imperative. The Gurobi optimiser can be tuned using a series of parameters described in detail in the solver’s documentation [42]. Gurobi offers a Parameter Tuning Tool, which iteratively solves a simplified version of the model while adjusting various parameters to find a combination that most effectively improves solution time. The tuning tool was used in combination with a series of customised adjustments to arrive at a solution time that proved suitable for scenario analysis. The chosen parameters are outlined in Table 16 and further explanation can be found in the solver’s documentation [42].

Because the Calliope model is linear, there are some limitations that have to be taken into account. First, pressure drop calculations are not taken into account within the model. The pressure drop calculations are performed separately and the pipeline capacities calculated based on the allowed pressure drop are used as input into the model (see also section 3.2.5). Additionally, no scaling factors to account for economics of scale could be used within the model. For the compressor CAPEX, a workaround is used where three flow regimes were used to calculate CAPEX numbers for low, mid and high flowrates (see also section 3.2.5).

Table 16: Gurobi tuning parameters used in model.

Gurobi Parameter	Description
MIPGap = 0.005 ¹²	The mixed integer problem (MIP) solver will end its optimisation with an optimal result when the gap between the lower and upper objective bound is less than the specified MIPGap (see [43]). This parameter is necessary since proving absolute optimality (MIPGap=0) of problems with such high degrees of complexity is not always feasible within reasonable timeframes, or at all.
Method = 2	Selecting the barrier method to solve the root relaxation of the MIP model.
Heuristics = 0.001	Set the fraction of total time spent on heuristics within total MIP runtime.
RINS = 500	Applies RINS heuristics at every 500 th node of the MIP search tree.
Cuts = 0	Disables generation of MIP cutting planes which can help speed up progress of the best bound during MIP model solving.
Presolve = 2	Enables more aggressive presolve algorithm.
MIPFocus = 3	Helps focus the model on the best objective bound to help it move more quickly.

¹² Base case scenario was run further until MIPGap = 0.00299 (total computational time: 40 hours 44 minutes) and no changes in grid configuration were observed when compared to MIPGap = 0.005. Alternative cases 1 through 4 were run to MIPGap = 0, due to their simplicity and therefore lesser degrees of computational intensity.

Although adjusting solver parameters can marginally improve runtime, the main driver impacting overall solution time is the complexity of the problem, which is impacted by the number of decision variables, the range of the bounds applied as constraints, and the number of timesteps of timeseries data used. The total number of decisions made by the model were limited and the available constraints tightened to such a degree that improved solution time without making the model entirely unrepresentative of reality.

To deal with high resolution data provided by the hourly timesteps (n=8760) used for wind resource, electricity market price, and demand profiles, the time masking feature of Calliope was utilised [39]. Time masking allows the model to look across a wide range of timeseries data and only “unmask” periods of relevance, such that they are considered at their full (hourly) resolution. All other “masked” periods of the year simply reflect the annual averages, an example of which is illustrated by Figure 3.

Figure 3: Example time-masking functionality.

This methodology was then validated by using the chosen network configuration of the model and fixing the installed capacities for each technology at the relevant nodes or arcs it recommended. The model was then re-run using Calliope’s “operational” mode, which mimics the operation of the system at full hourly resolution, deciding on optimal energy flows using the fixed technologies and capacities specified.¹³ In doing so, the chosen compressors, pipelines, purifiers, etc., were affirmed to be the appropriate capacity and configuration for proper system operation at every hourly timestep of the year.

3.2.5 Input data

Supply technologies

The sources of hydrogen supply used in the model are summarised in Table 17. While investment costs (CAPEX) are taken into consideration for conversion and transmission technologies (e.g., compressors, pipelines, etc.), they are disregarded for supply technologies, which are assumed to already be in existence. Therefore, the model makes assumptions based on only marginal costs of operation for the sources of hydrogen supply.

¹³ See [69] for further details on the functioning of Calliope’s operational mode.

Table 17: Techno-economic constraints for supply technologies. *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

	Electrolyser	Biogasification	LOHC Import	LH ₂ Import	Backbone	Alternative HRS supply
Installed Capacity (MW _{H₂})	200	7.4	100	75	200	-
Supply pressure (bar)	30	8	1	16	30	350
Supply purity*	hq	mq	lq	mq	lq	hq
Energy intensity (MW _e /MW _{H₂})	1.48	0.055	-	-	-	-
Variable OPEX (electricity market price x energy intensity)	yes	yes	-	-	-	-
Fixed OPEX (€/MW _{H₂})	-	13.5	81	87.54	144.29	150

The electrolyser is assumed to have an operating efficiency of 67.5% [44] and a maximum output capacity of 200 MW_{H₂}. The variable OPEX (€/MW_{H₂}) is calculated using the assumed efficiency and the market price of electricity described by the Electricity price profile below.

The biogasification plant has a fixed OPEX of 13.5 €/MW_{H₂} assuming recycled wood clippings will be used as feedstock for the biogasification plant with an approximate cost of 0.045 €/kg [45] and an approximate efficiency of 300 kg of biomass needed per MW_{H₂} produced (10 kg biomass per kg H₂) [46]. The energy intensity of biogasification is assumed to be 0.055 MW_e/MW_{H₂} (1.84 kWh per kg H₂) [46], and the variable OPEX (€/MW_{H₂}) is calculated using this value and the market price of electricity. The hydrogen purity is assumed to be medium quality (≥99.5% and <99.999%) and the pressure is assumed to be 8 bar (although the output pressure could feasibly be closer to 10 bar, it is assumed to be slightly lower to feed into the 8 bar pressure layer of the model) [47].

Imported hydrogen in the model is assumed to be either liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHC) or liquified hydrogen (LH₂) based on anticipated imports into the Port of Amsterdam [48]. LOHC is assumed to be low-quality (98%) and low-pressure (1 bar) due to the dehydrogenation step required to regenerate hydrogen [49] [50]. LH₂ is expected to be medium-quality (99.5%) assuming it is green hydrogen produced by an electrolyser abroad but cannot maintain the highest quality (99.999%) needed for mobility applications throughout the value chain [50]. The pressure is assumed to be 20 bar [49], but in the model 16 bar is used to match the option of the 16 bar pipeline. The assumed pressure and purity from LOHC and LH₂ imports are substantiated by HyDelta 3 D1a.1 [49] but there remains some degree of uncertainty when it comes to the actual pressure, purity, and volumes that can be expected for imported hydrogen. For practical reasons, these general assumptions are maintained for the purpose of this modelling exercise, but the results should be interpreted with such assumptions in mind. The anticipated marginal costs of using imported LOHC (81 €/MW_{H₂}) and LH₂ (87.54 €/MW_{H₂}) are approximated from previous research [51] [41].

Hydrogen is expected to be available from HNS via a 200 MW_{H₂} connection, which is assumed to be continuously available. The cost is approximated from previous literature [41] that estimated the average H₂ market price in the Netherlands to be 66.1 €/MW_{H₂} but which also expected much lower costs for imports (e.g., LH₂ price of 42.59 €/MW_{H₂}). Therefore, the Dutch H₂ market price was scaled by a comparable proportion to 144.29 €/MW_{H₂}, such that the backbone price would be the same

relative proportion to the chosen import price (a factor of approximately 1.6). The purity from the backbone is assumed to be 98% although the final purity that HNS will use remains undecided at this time, with recent guidance recommending a higher purity of 99.5% [50].

The alternative supply for the hydrogen refueling station (HRS) reflects the marginal cost of sourcing high-purity hydrogen from another region via truck. The marginal costs are calculated in a similar manner to the truck calculations described further below (see Trucks) but using a distance of 112 km to account for higher costs of truck transport from a distant region (e.g., Rotterdam). The estimated investment costs of production (or import) of H₂, compression, purification, and truck CAPEX are also built into the final cost as lifetime costs per MW_{H₂} transported. Additionally, the OPEX for the purification step and truck transport are also built into the final costs. The available supply profile provided to this technology matches the demand profile of the HRS exactly, such that there is no excess high-purity hydrogen that can be fed into the distribution system. The intention is to prevent the model from being forced to install a PSA unit only to satisfy minimal HRS demand if the electrolyser (which is the only other source of fuel-cell grade hydrogen in the system) is periodically unable to meet demand. In practice, it would likely make more sense to have local on-site storage and source high-purity hydrogen from another region rather than installing an expensive PSA unit with incredibly low utilization.

Supply and demand profiles

Anonymized demand profiles for heat and feedstock end-users for the H2avennet base case were obtained from the DSOs. The mobility demand curve is obtained from HyDelta 1 D7a.2 [52] and the volume assumes an HRS with an approximate supply of 1000 kg per day and 75% utilization. A simplified overview of these demand profiles is given in Figure 4. The mobility demand is constant throughout the year but displays daily fluctuations. In particular, the mobility demand is relatively high each day between 07:00 and 21:00 and reaches its minimum during the night. There are several end-users with a heat demand. The total heat demand profile of all end-users is more irregular but typically displays a stable base demand, though there are often peaks on top of that demand and less frequently dips below that demand. The profile for feedstock demand is typically a stable demand both throughout the day and the year, with the exception of a few moments.

The supply profile of the electrolyser is based on the wind supply profile of a 300 MW_e windfarm adapted from [53], and always operates at a minimum of 10% of the total electrolyser capacity (i.e., minimum electrolyser supply is 20 MW_{H₂}). The biomass supply profile is either full capacity (7.4 MW_{H₂}) or shut off (however, there are certain periods where not all 7.4 MW are produced for system balancing purposes and in reality, some small-scale storage might be necessary, but this is outside of the model scope). The import is assumed to be constant throughout the year and is a sum of the backbone supply, liquid H₂ import and liquid organic hydrogen carrier (LOHC) import. For the base case scenario, it is assumed that at moments when the total hydrogen supply (e.g., from electrolyser, biomass, and imports) exceeds total demand, the excess will be exported to the backbone. Although a 200 MW_{H₂} HNS connection is expected, exports are capped at 190 MW to ensure model feasibility by providing a small buffer between available supply and demand.

Figure 4: Simplified overview of demand profiles for mobility, heat and feedstock in MW_{H₂} and supply profiles for the electrolyser, biomass gasification plant and import (including the HNS backbone connection).

Electricity price profile

The electricity price profile (see Figure 5) is based on calculated hourly prices for the Netherlands for 2030 [41]. To account for increased electricity price expectations since this study, the electricity profile is multiplied by a factor 1.39, based on [54].

Figure 5: Assumed electricity price profile.

Compression

All compressor technologies in the model are assumed to be reciprocating compressors. All general assumptions can be seen in Table 18. Detailed cost assumptions are explained in Table 19.

Table 18: General assumptions relating to compressor technologies.

Constraint	Value	Description
Maximum installed energy capacity	400 MW	Model can install up to a 400 MW compressor at any node
Minimum installed energy capacity	0 MW	Model can install 0 MW of compressors at no cost at nodes where compression is not necessary
Fixed annual OPEX	5%	Assumes fixed OPEX of 5% of total CAPEX per year
Energy efficiency	1.0	Negligible hydrogen losses through compressors from leakages
Lifetime	15 years [55]	

There are many different equations available in literature to calculate compressor CAPEX, though these often result in large differences for the cost estimations. Compressor costs from several CAPEX equations were compared with compressor supplier information to identify three models that were most appropriate to use for compressor CAPEX calculations [56]. Other models, and especially the linear model, significantly overestimated the CAPEX. One of these three models that were deemed appropriate is used in this research to calculate the compressor CAPEX [57]:

$$CAPEX = 5256 P^{0.82} \quad (5)$$

In which 5256 is the specific compressor costs in € kW^{-0.82}, P is the compressor power in kW which is calculated by multiplying eqn. (6) with the flow rate in kg s⁻¹, and 0.82 is a scaling factor to account for economies of scale. In the Calliope model, the CAPEX has to be provided in € MW⁻¹. Due to the scaling factor in the CAPEX equations, this equation cannot directly be applied in the model. Therefore, several flow regimes have been considered, for which the CAPEX of the lower bound and upper bound are calculated and the average of these values is used for the compressors within that flow regime. The low-flow regime was determined for flows up to 18 MW off-taker H₂ demand, the mid-flow regime was determined for flows between 18 MW and 116 MW and the high-flow regime was determined for flows between 116 MW and 232 MW off-taker H₂ demand (Table 19). For the base case, the mid-flow compressor costs are only applicable to those installed near the LOHC import terminal and the HNS backbone, which happen to fall in this flow range, while all other compressors installed in the model fall in the low-flow range.

Table 19: Overview of assumptions on compressor CAPEX and electricity usage.

Compression	CAPEX (€/MW _{H₂}) low-flow, up to 18 MW	CAPEX (€/MW _{H₂}) mid-flow, 18-116 MW	CAPEX (€/MW _{H₂}) high-flow, 116- 232 MW	Electricity consumption (MWh _e /MWh _{H₂})
1 to 4 bar	47670	34343	26958	0.02244
4 to 8 bar	27956	20141	15810	0.01171
8 to 16 bar	28013	20182	15842	0.01174
16 to 30 bar	25860	18631	14624	0.01065
30 to 350 bar	77382	55749	43760	0.04052
350 to 700 bar	33084	23835	18709	0.01438

The variable OPEX for the compressor is calculated by multiplying the electricity price by the relative electricity intensity of each compression range (e.g., the electricity consumption ratio in MW_e/MW_{H_2}). The energy consumption ratio of a compressor is calculated by:

$$\frac{Power}{Q} = \frac{NZ}{\eta_i \eta_m} \frac{RT}{Mw} \frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1} \left[\left(\frac{P_2}{P_1} \right)^{\frac{(\gamma-1)}{N\gamma}} - 1 \right] \quad (6)$$

In which $Power/Q$ is the energy consumption ratio in MW_e/MW_{H_2} . N is the number of compressor stages, which is assumed to be 2 for all compressors. Z is the hydrogen compressibility factor, assumed to be 1.0006 for 1 bar; 1.0025 at 4 bar; 1.0050 at 8 bar; 1.0100 at 16 bar; 1.0188 at 30 bar; 1.0967 at 150 bar; 1.231 at 350 bar, all at 0°C [58]. The compressibility factors at 0° were used as this was the closest available temperature for which the numbers were provided. In reality, the temperature in hydrogen pipelines in the Netherlands is typically between 5°C and 15°C and an increase in temperature leads to slightly lower compressibility factors. This means that the numbers used are a slight overestimation, leading to slightly higher energy consumption. R is the gas constant, $8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. T is the temperature, assumed to be 283.15K. η_i is isentropic efficiency and is based on the compression ratio per stage and is assumed to be 78.4% for 1-4 bar compression; 71.5% for 4-8 bar; 71.5% for 8-16 bar; 71.5% for 16-30 bar; 79.8% for 30-150 bar; 79.8% for 150-700 bar; 85.0% for 30-350 bar; 71.5% for 350-700 bar [59]. η_m is the motor efficiency, assumed to be 85% [59]. M_w is the molecular mass of hydrogen, 2.016 g/mol. γ is the heat capacity ratio for H_2 , 1.41 at 20°C. P is the pressure in Pa.

Purification

Two different purification technologies are considered in the model: pressure swing adsorption (PSA) and polymeric membranes. In pressure swing adsorption, the low-quality hydrogen gas stream is led through an adsorbent column at high pressure (30 bar). The impurities get adsorbed by the adsorbent bed while hydrogen passes through the bed and exits the column at high purity and high pressure (30 bar). The adsorbent bed is then regenerated by decreasing the pressure to 1 bar. While the PSA operating pressure is 30 bar, in the model the pressure inlet for the PSA is set to 1 bar (see Table 20) in order to make it accept all gas streams above 1 bar. This is done to prevent the installation of an additional compressor located directly next to the PSA since the PSA already contains a compressor able to compress the gas stream from 1 to 30 bar. During initial model validation, the OPEX was calculated using a middle-of-the-road assumption that incoming hydrogen streams to the PSA would only need to be pressurized on average from 16 to 30 bar during the purification process. However, initial results made clear that PSAs were only installed at the LOHC import terminal, where the supply is 1 bar, thus the OPEX was recalculated assuming that hydrogen would be compressed from 1 to 30 bar during the purification process, resulting in higher, but more accurate, OPEX costs.

Alternatively, hydrogen can be purified by polymeric membranes. In this technology, the separation is based on permeability of the gases through the membrane. The driving force of membrane separation is the pressure difference across the membranes. A pressure difference of 30 bar is assumed for the polymeric membranes in this model, meaning the low-quality hydrogen gas stream enters the membranes at 30 bar and the medium-quality hydrogen gas stream exits the membranes at 1 bar. Note that with polymer membranes a maximum H_2 purity of 99.7% can be reached, which is assigned to medium-quality hydrogen in the model. For a more thorough discussion between different purification technologies, the reader is referred to the HyDelta 3 D1a.1 report [49].

General assumptions used in the model such as capacities, CAPEX, technology lifetime, and operational & maintenance costs can be found in Table 20. For both purification technologies, the

presence of sulfur in the hydrogen gas stream can pose challenges, and it should be removed before entering the PSA column or the membranes [49]. Such a pre-treatment step of the hydrogen gas stream is not considered in this research. To ensure that possible hydrogen leaks can be detected by smell, it is considered to odorize distribution grids with tetrahydrothiophene (THT), which is also used for natural gas odorization. However, since THT contains sulfur, this could have a serious impact on the optimal grid configuration and the total system costs as it could require additional purification at the end-users. For the purpose of this research, we assume that end-users do not require additional removal of THT from the gas streams, as it is highly dependent on the specific end-use and we instead aim to keep the results generalizable. However, the impact on the base case grid configuration of having to remove THT from H₂ at the end-user location is discussed further in section 4.1.2.

The relative electricity intensity of the PSA (in MW_e/MW_{H₂}) is simplified to the energy consumption related to the compression of the hydrogen gas streams to the desired operating pressure (30 bar), using eqn. (6) (see Table 20). The variable OPEX of a PSA is calculated by multiplying the electricity price by the relative electricity intensity of compression and then dividing by 0.85 to account for a H₂ recovery rate of 85%.

Table 20: Overview techno-economic input data for hydrogen purification technologies, most of the values are retrieved from HyDelta 3 D1a.1 [49]. *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

Purification technology	PSA	Polymer
Capacity min (MW _{H₂})	69.9	2.8
Capacity max (MW _{H₂})	833	233
Min load (MW _{H₂})	12.6	-
Pressure in (bar)	1	30
Pressure out (bar)	30	1
Purity range*	lq-hq	lq-mq
Fixed investment costs (M€/unit)	4	0.1
Additional CAPEX scale (€/MW _{H₂})	7501	3000
Lifetime (years)	20	5
O&M costs (% of CAPEX/year)	5%	0.5%
Electricity usage (kWh _e /kWh _{H₂})	0.05861	-
H ₂ recovery rate (%)	85%	70%

Pipelines

The temperature of H₂ in the pipeline is assumed to be 10°C and the H₂ velocity in the pipeline should always be lower than 60 m/s. The pipeline capacity is calculated based on a max 40% pressure drop over the maximum distance in the region. The maximum distance for the base case is assumed to be half of the total pipeline length in the H2avennet layout. For the “typical” alternative case (see section 4.3.6), the pipeline length is based on the average layout of the indicated pipeline length for 11 hydrogen areas in the HyRegions report [60], adjusted for the number of connections.

An exception to the 40% pressure drop was made for the pipelines at 30 bar, for which a max 5% pressure drop was accepted. The high pressure drop was assumed to be acceptable for feedstock and heat end-users (with pressures < 16 bar) since their pressure demand is assumed to be relatively flexible (e.g., the liquid H₂ supply pressure is 16 bar but we assume feedstock end-users can accept pressures 40% lower than 16 bar without issue). A max 5% pressure drop was considered for the 30 bar pipeline because initial simulations for the base case showed that a 30 bar pipeline is only installed to transport H₂ from the electrolyser to the HNS backbone or the mobility demand, which both require

a pressure as high as possible (since the H₂ needs to be further compressed to 60 or 700 bar, respectively). While in theory the 30 bar pipeline could also supply other end-users, this is not typically seen as H₂ from the LOHC and LH₂ import have lower marginal costs than the 30 bar H₂ supply sources, and therefore, it is more cost-optimal to install a lower-pressure pipeline for these end-users. Alternatively, a 30 bar pipeline could be preferably installed because of its large capacity. However, the pipeline capacity for lower pressure pipelines is already sufficient to handle all H₂ flows for the base case¹⁴ because the pipeline diameter of 0.3 m that is planned for the H2avennet distribution grid is relatively large.

The pipeline CAPEX in €/km is calculated by eqn. (7) (in which D is the diameter in inches) that is obtained from the ACER report, and this formula is corrected with HyWay27 numbers [61] [3].

$$Investment\ costs = 1021.7 \times D^2 - 20393 \times D + 642720 \quad (7)$$

Based on consultation with grid operators, pipeline CAPEX is assumed to be higher for 16 and 30 bar pipelines where steel is used than for 4 and 8 bar pipelines where PE100 is used. Material costs for steel compared to PE100 are expected to be roughly 15% greater based on expert consultation. Thus, a 15% increase in CAPEX is added to the material cost of pipelines, which is assumed to be roughly one-third of the total CAPEX according to ACER [61]. Although practically there are further cost discrepancies between 16 and 30 bar pipelines, with the latter requiring stronger material, the cost difference is assumed to be negligible for simplification of the model, but the results should be interpreted with this in mind. The pipeline OPEX (in €/km/year) is assumed to be 1% of the pipeline CAPEX. Although this figure could be an underestimate in some cases, even when pipeline CAPEX was increased by 25% (see section 4.2.5), the grid configuration changed very minimally, suggesting that slightly higher annual OPEX would also have limited impact on the results.

Table 21: Overview of assumptions used for calculation of the pipeline costs.

Scenario	Max distance (km)	Diameter (m)	Pressure (bar)	Max energetic flow rate (MW _{H2})	CAPEX (€/km)
H2avennet base case	13	0.3	4	98	1068041
	13	0.3	8	202	1068041
	13	0.3	16	412	1119841
	13	0.3	30	298 ^a	1119841
Average case	27	0.3	4	66	1068041
	27	0.3	8	137	1068041
	27	0.3	16	282	1119841
	27	0.3	30	204 ^a	1119841

^a A pressure drop of max 5% is assumed for the 30 bar pipeline, while a pressure drop of max 40% is assumed for the other pipelines.

Trucks

The general technical and economic assumptions made regarding tube trailer transport of hydrogen via truck in the model are given in Table 22.

¹⁴ The average utilised capacity of the pipelines for the base-case is about 60% of the total pipeline capacity.

Table 22: General technical and cost assumptions for trucks.

Scenario	Pressure (bar)	Trailer capacity (kg)	Trailer lifetime (years)	Hourly truck capacity (MW/h)	CAPEX (€)	Fixed OPEX (€/year)	Variable OPEX (€/MW _{H₂})	Assumed distance (km)
H2avennet base case	350	900	12	5.27	825572	28509	3.55	5.3
Average case	350	900	12	4.94	825572	28509	3.68	11.0

The trailer capacity, lifetime, fixed OPEX, and CAPEX were all adapted from [62] and cost figures were corrected for 2024 inflation. The assumed pressure of 350 bar and expected trailer loading time (used below) were selected after consultation with a local HRS and tube trailer operator. The variable OPEX and hourly truck capacity calculations were made using equations (8) through (12) adapted from [52].

$$trips = \frac{365 \times utilisation \left[\frac{hours}{day} \right]}{2 \times \left(\frac{distance[km]}{driving\ speed \left[\frac{km}{hour} \right]} + loading\ time[hours] \right)} \quad (8)$$

$$annual\ fuel\ cost \left[\frac{€}{year} \right] = 2 \times distance[km] \times trips \times consumption \left[\frac{liters}{km} \right] \times price \left[\frac{€}{liter} \right] \quad (9)$$

$$annual\ wage\ costs \left[\frac{€}{year} \right] = 365 \times utilisation \left[\frac{hours}{day} \right] \times driver\ wage \left[\frac{€}{hour} \right] \quad (10)$$

$$annual\ truck\ volume \left[\frac{MWh}{year} \right] = trips \times trailer\ capacity \quad (11)$$

$$variable\ OPEX \left[\frac{€}{MW_{H_2}} \right] = \frac{annual\ fuel\ costs + annual\ wage\ costs}{annual\ truck\ volume} \quad (12)$$

The number of possible trips in a year is calculated using equation (8), where utilization is 18 hours [52], distance is dependent on the scenarios shown in Table 22, driving speed is 40 km/hour, and loading time is 2 hours. The annual fuel costs are then calculated using equation (9), where distance and trips are known from equation (8), fuel consumption is 0.21 liters/km [62], and fuel price is 1.83 €/liter (average diesel price in the Netherlands from 2022 to 2024) [63]. Annual wage costs are calculated using equation (10) where driver wage is 24 €/hour [62]. The variable OPEX, annual, and hourly truck volumes are calculated accordingly using equations (11) and (12). Using variable OPEX (€ per MW_{H₂} transported on a given arc) in the model ensures that OPEX costs (fuel and wages) are not overestimated due to low volumes of HRS demand that would require fewer hours of truck utilization

than might be typically expected.¹⁵ The CAPEX and fixed OPEX could also be calculated based on the actual HRS demand, i.e. a cost per MW_{H_2} , which could represent hiring a truck instead of purchasing because of the low utilization. However, in reality a rented truck would not always be available on short term during those hours that it is required to balance the system. Therefore, it is assumed that the truck is purchased even though the CAPEX and fixed OPEX costs could overestimate reality, which would likely not justify such expenditures for low hours of utilization.

¹⁵ For instance, given the mobility demand profile utilized in the base case scenario, a truck would only need to make one trip per day to satisfy demand.

4. Modelling results on cost optimized grid characteristics

The results of the model are discussed in the following sections, beginning first with a detailed account of the optimal solution found for the base case scenario, which uses the H2avennet network layout and allows the model to install 4, 8, 16, and 30 bar pipelines on any arc, with no restriction on the number of pipelines it can install (section 4.1). Section 4.2 follows with a series of sensitivities that were performed on the base case to test the robustness of the model. Finally, section 4.3 describes the results of alternative scenarios that were conducted and how their results compare to the base case.

Before discussing the results, it is important to reiterate that while the H2avennet network is the inspiration for the base case layout, the real-life H2avennet case has many additional complexities that cannot reasonably be incorporated into the model. For instance, it is likely that rather than a single HNS connection for the whole network, some off-takers will have both a direct connection to HNS and a connection to the H2avennet network, meaning multiple feed-in points from the national infrastructure could be present in the grid. Many technical details such as this are kept out of the model scope for simplification and to attempt to keep the base case general enough such that the insights obtained from sensitivities and scenarios can inform planning decisions for future decentral hydrogen regions.

4.1 Results base case based on H2avennet project

The most optimal pipeline configuration leading to the lowest total system cost for the base case is depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Grid configuration for base case *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

Table 23: Conversion technologies (MW_{H₂}, throughput) installed in the base case.

ID	Compression	Purification	Other
*a	51 MW 4-30 bar (lq) 6.6 MW 1-30 bar (mq)	6.6 MW polymer	
*b	98 MW 1-4 bar (lq)		
*c	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)		Alternate truck supply
*d	7.1 MW 8-16 bar (mq)		

When interpreting the resulting pipeline configuration, it is important to note that grids can be interconnected to ensure feasibility and match supply with demand. In other words, higher pressure pipelines can feed into lower pressure networks at any node, so long as purification is not required (e.g., a 30 bar low-quality pipeline could feed into a low-quality 8 bar pipeline but **not** a medium-quality pipeline unless a polymer or PSA is installed). For instance, the 16 bar medium-quality pipeline shown in Figure 6 could depressurise and feed into the low-quality 4 bar network at any node where the two grids overlap. This interconnection between networks improves balancing within the network, ensures the model is feasible, and improves security of supply.

The most-optimal grid configuration shown in Figure 6 includes a large low-quality 4 bar pipeline network that provides all heat demand nodes with H₂ from the LOHC import terminal, which supplies 1 bar low-quality hydrogen at the lowest marginal cost of all supply nodes. A slightly smaller medium-quality 16 bar pipeline network connects all feedstock demand nodes with the liquid H₂ import terminal, which has the second lowest marginal cost after LOHC imports. It is clear that the end-users are connected to the grid whose pressure and quality characteristics most closely match their demand (e.g., heat off-takers with 1 bar low-quality demand connect to the 4 bar low-quality grid, while feedstock off-takers with 16 bar medium-quality demand connect to the 16 bar grid).

Additionally, there is a relatively short medium-quality 30 bar pipeline that connects the HNS backbone with the electrolyser, which is typically used for feeding H₂ from the electrolyser into the HNS backbone. Between the electrolyser and the HRS there is a small high-quality 30 bar pipeline, feeding the high-quality high-pressure H₂ obtained from the electrolyser directly to the HRS, where it is compressed to 700 bar. Such a high-pressure and quality pipeline prevents additional compression and purification costs that would be required at the HRS if a lower-quality and/or pressure pipeline had been installed. This is the only arc where the model could choose to transport via truck instead of pipeline, but it is hypothesised that at such short distances, pipelines are preferable. In fact, the model only opted for truck transport when high-quality pipelines were not possible in the re-use of existing pipeline infrastructure sensitivity (4.2.7).

The installed capacities of the compressors, purification technology and alternative HRS supply in this most optimal configuration are also depicted Figure 6 and Table 23. Further description is offered below:

- H₂ supplied by the LOHC import terminal has a pressure of 1 bar. Nevertheless, since its marginal costs are relatively low, the model typically decides a high amount of LOHC import is optimal. In order to feed this 1 bar H₂ stream into any of the pipeline options, it requires a compressor of considerable size to be installed.
- The biomass gasification plant produces H₂ at 8 bar. Since the model does not choose to install an 8 bar pipeline, it is compressed to 16 bar in order to feed into the 16 bar pipeline.

- The HRS obtains H₂ from two different sources: i) from the electrolyser via a high-quality 30 bar pipeline; ii) imported by truck from outside of the base case region. Between these two options, approximately two-thirds of the total demand is sourced from the HRS supply trucks and the remaining third is sourced from the electrolyser. A small compressor is installed at the HRS node to compress H₂ to the desired pressure. A 30 to 700 bar compressor is installed, but as most of the H₂ is sourced from the HRS supply trucks, the majority of the time it will only compress from 350 to 700 bar.
- At the HNS backbone node, a polymer membrane purification plant and two compressors are installed. The polymer membranes and one relatively small compressor are required to convert low-purity hydrogen from the 4 bar pipeline (coming from the LOHC terminal) into medium-quality 30 bar hydrogen that can be fed into the corresponding pipeline. Another large compressor is installed in order to feed H₂ from the 4 bar pipeline into the HNS backbone.

The total system costs of the base case are approximately €249.87 million and are displayed in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Total system costs (left) and breakdown of conversion and transmission costs (right) for base case scenario.

The majority of the total system costs, roughly €243.7 million, is related to the marginal production costs of H₂ from imports and the electrolyser. For the base case, the electrolyser was forced to run following a wind resource profile. It is thus not surprising that the electrolyser is one of the biggest contributors to the total production costs. The other big contributor is H₂ import, which can be attributed to its relatively low marginal cost, and therefore, high utilisation. The conversion and transmission costs (Figure 7 - right) represent a small portion of the total system costs, roughly €6 million in total, with the compressors being the major factor and the pipelines a lower but still significant contributor. Considerable CAPEX investments in conversion and distribution infrastructure in such projects can often be the primary hurdle to overcome and therefore should receive close consideration even though they represent a comparably small share of total system costs compared to system OPEX [1].

4.1.1 Base case hourly operational results

The base case scenario was also run in Calliope's operational mode to assess hourly operation of the system with the compressor, purification, and pipeline capacities determined by the model as described in section 3.2.4. The results can be seen in Figure 8. The full load hours of the electrolyser are 4427. The total system costs of the model run in operational mode validate that the time masking functionality is a fair representation of reality, as they differed by less than 0.5% (€249.9 vs 248.7

million for the base case and operational mode, respectively) when taking into account all hourly operating costs for the entire year.

Figure 8: Hourly energy flow of base case scenario (*total demand line = end-user demand + backbone export).

4.1.2 Limitations of base case

The model selected multiple pipelines at different quality and pressure levels, which may seem counterintuitive, particularly for arcs where three pipelines are selected in parallel with one another. Since the model's objective function simply aims to minimise the total system cost, the "optimal" network might overlook certain practical considerations and the results should be interpreted with these in mind. For instance, space constraints are outside of the model scope. In reality, there is limited area available for trenching pipelines between nodes, which certainly could limit the potential for installing multiple pipelines in parallel. Consultation with distribution grid operators made clear that a single pressure layer network is most conventional from a simplicity and space perspective. Thus, it is important to compare the total system cost of the "optimal" (yet complex) base case with scenarios that limit the network to one or two pressure layers (section 4.3) and weigh the cost savings against other practical considerations.

As noted in section 3.2.5, the additional purification that would be required if THT were added as an odorant to the distribution grid was not considered. However, if it had been included in the model, one could expect to see certain changes in the resulting configuration. For instance, a high-quality 30 bar pipeline between the electrolyser and a mobility end-user is unlikely since the presence of sulfur at concentrations of only 1 ppm leads to irreversible damage to fuel cells [64]. Therefore, the use of THT would require additional purification at the HRS and transport by tube trailer would become more attractive. For end-users with heat demand no insurmountable hurdles are expected if an odorant is added to the distribution grid as the combustion equipment utilized for these applications is relatively robust [64]. For feedstock applications the impact of odorization is more difficult to predict, as the impact of sulfur is highly case-specific. Nevertheless, an additional purification step is expected to be required for certain feedstock end-users, which would increase the total system cost.

4.2 Results sensitivity analysis

Before discussing the outcomes of the alternative scenarios, it is important to examine the model’s sensitivity to changing key parameters.

4.2.1 Rearranged grid lay-out

The location of hydrogen supply and demand nodes in the grid layout affects the most optimal pipeline configuration. The locations of the supply and demand nodes in the grid layout for the base case, as depicted in Figure 6, were more-or-less randomly chosen. The extent to what the optimal pipeline configuration is influenced by the location of the supply and demand nodes (e.g., are similar pipelines chosen but connecting different nodes, or are completely different pipelines optimal) was determined by randomly rearranging the supply and demand nodes within the grid layout as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Grid configuration of base case (above) versus sensitivity with rearranged layout (below) *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

The pipeline configuration of the rearranged supply and demand nodes is very similar to the base case. Naturally, the pipelines are installed at different nodes, but mostly the same type of pipelines are chosen:

- High-quality 30 bar pipeline to connect the electrolyser and the HRS.
- Medium-quality 16 bar pipeline to connect liquid H₂ import terminal with feedstock end-users.
- Low-quality 4 bar pipeline to connect the LOHC terminal with heat end-users.

Some small differences compared to the base case were also observed. In the base case, H₂ from the biomass gasification plant is directly compressed to 16 bar and fed into the medium-quality 16 bar pipeline. In this sensitivity analysis, the biomass gasification plant is not located directly next to the medium-quality 16 bar pipeline, and therefore, an additional medium-quality 8 bar pipeline is installed that connects to the 16 bar pipeline. For this transmission arc, an 8 bar pipeline is installed instead of a 16 bar pipeline, as these cost slightly less due to lower material costs. Another difference is that in the base case a medium-quality 30 bar pipeline is installed between the electrolyser and the backbone which is mainly used to feed from the electrolyser into the backbone. In the sensitivity analysis, part

of this pathway is connected through a high-quality 30 bar pipeline (which is required for the HRS), and the other part is connected through a low-quality 30 bar pipeline.

Some noticeable differences are observed in the compressors installed in this sensitivity compared to the base case, with more compressors needed overall to accommodate the new 8 bar pipelines. This results in slightly higher compression costs but similar total systems due to the lower cost of pipelines in this sensitivity where feedstock demand is more concentrated, thus requiring a smaller 16 bar grid (which has higher CAPEX than 4 or 8 bar pipelines).

Overall, the results from this sensitivity analysis underline the robustness of the model, as the locations of supply and demand nodes within the basic layout only minimally affect the type of pipeline and compressors installed by the model.

4.2.2 Decrease compression costs

Decreasing compressor CAPEX by 25% allowed for testing the sensitivity of the network configuration to compression costs. Although the pipeline layout remained unchanged from the base case when compression CAPEX was lowered, it did result in an additional 6 MW compressor being installed such that the 16 bar grid could feed into the 30 bar grid to connect the sources supplying the 16 bar grid (LH₂ import and biomass) to the backbone for export. However, given the lack of change observed in the pipeline layout and only a minor change with the additional compressor that is utilised infrequently, this sensitivity does not suggest that lower compression costs would result in vastly different outcomes.

4.2.3 Decrease purification costs

The purification costs were decreased by 25% in order to assess how the number of purification units and pipelines will change if the purification costs would turn out to be lower than anticipated. However, no changes were observed in the pipeline layout, compressor placement or capacity, nor the purification placement or capacity. The single 6.55 MW polymeric membrane was still placed at the backbone location in this sensitivity, just as it was in the base case. Therefore, this result suggests lower purification costs would not result in vastly different outcomes.

4.2.4 Higher mobility demand

In the base case, there is only one HRS with a small demand (average demand is about 1 MW per hour), and therefore, it has a small impact on the decision-making process for the pipeline configuration. To investigate whether a significantly increased mobility demand would affect the pipeline configuration and the installed conversion technologies, a sensitivity analysis was performed with mobility demand volumes increased by a factor 10. This demand could represent a future scenario in which the HRS serves not only road mobility but also marine mobility or fuel-cell applications for backup power. However, no significant changes in the pipeline configuration or the installed conversion technologies were observed. Thus, even a significantly increased HRS demand is still not high enough to change the pipeline grid configuration to higher pressure or quality that would be required for the HRS.

4.2.5 Higher pipeline CAPEX

In the base case, multiple pipelines at different quality and pressure levels were installed for the “optimal” pipeline configuration. This may seem counterintuitive, particularly for arcs where multiple pipelines are selected in parallel with one another. It was hypothesized that this could be caused by an underestimation of the pipeline CAPEX. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis was performed in which the pipeline CAPEX was increased by 25%.

The pipeline configuration of this sensitivity analysis is very similar to the configuration of the base case (Figure 10). The biggest difference is the absence of the medium-quality 16 bar pipeline that was in the base case located between the middle feedstock demand node and the electrolyser. Since the medium-quality 16 bar pipeline coming from the liquid H₂ terminal no longer supplies H₂ to the rightmost feedstock node, a small additional pipeline is installed to connect to the HNS backbone. At the location of the HNS backbone, additionally a larger 16 to 30 bar compressor is installed, such that the H₂ coming from the liquid H₂ import terminal can be compressed to 30 bar and fed into the backbone. Overall, the similarity between this sensitivity analysis and the base case indicates that a higher pipeline CAPEX does not significantly affect the total pipeline configuration.

Figure 10: Grid configuration of base case (above) versus sensitivity with higher pipeline CAPEX (below) *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

4.2.6 Only low-quality demand for end-users

Purification technologies are expensive and, if chosen to be installed, can lead to a considerable increase in CAPEX investments. Pipelines on the other hand are relatively cheap compared to purification technologies. Therefore, it was hypothesized that the base case may install multiple pipelines to prevent installation of purification technologies. A sensitivity analysis was performed to test this hypothesis, by changing the quality of demand to low-quality for all feedstock end-users. This isolates the demand pressure as the decisive factor for determining the pipeline configuration. Additionally, this sensitivity provides interesting insights for regions without feedstock consumers.

The general pipeline configuration of this sensitivity analysis is similar to the base case (Figure 11). There is still a 30 bar pipeline connecting the electrolyser with the backbone, a 16 bar pipeline connecting liquid H₂ with most of the feedstock end-users, and a 4 bar pipeline connecting LOHC import with the majority of the heat demand end-users.

Figure 11: Grid configuration of base case (above) versus sensitivity with only low-quality demand (below) *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

Nevertheless, aside from the pipelines now all being low-quality, there are several deviations from the base case. Most notably, less double or triple pipelines are installed between nodes. The main differences are listed below:

- The 4 bar low-quality pipeline that in the base case is installed between the biomass and the rightmost heat demand node is omitted in this scenario and the heat demand is supplied by the 16 bar pipeline that also connects the feedstock node close by.
- The medium-quality 16 bar pipeline that in the base case is installed between the biomass and the upper feedstock demand node is not installed in this scenario as this feedstock demand can now be satisfied by simply compressing the 4 bar low-quality H₂ coming from the LOHC input terminal. In the base case this would have also required purification, which is an expensive technology, and therefore, the model preferred to install double pipelines.
- This scenario installed a short additional pipeline compared to the base case, connecting the HNS backbone with the 16 bar pipeline that was already present close by, likely because the backbone can now also directly serve the feedstock demand while in the base case it would have needed an additional purification step.

Despite of all these simplifications in the pipeline configuration due to the low-quality feedstock demand, the total system cost of this scenario was only marginally lower (< €0.5 million) than that of the base case.

4.2.7 Reuse existing pipelines

If not all hydrogen infrastructure needs to be newly constructed, but some of the old natural gas infrastructure could be reused, the pipeline cost would be considerably lower. The effect of such a large decrease in pipeline costs (30% of original CAPEX according to [52]) is investigated in a sensitivity analysis. As expected, the model now installs a large number of additional pipelines because the costs are very cheap compared to all other technologies. Additionally, a truck is now required to transport hydrogen from the electrolyser to the HRS as reused pipelines are not able to maintain fuel cell quality

during transport. The total system costs are slightly lower (€0.8 million) compared to the base case, but such a small margin likely does not outweigh the challenges that come from operating such a complex pipeline grid.

4.3 Results alternative cases

4.3.1 Alternative case 1: only medium-quality 16 bar pipelines

The base case, as discussed in Section 4.1, gave an optimal pipeline configuration consisting of multiple pipelines with different quality and pressure levels. Between certain nodes up to three different pipelines were chosen by the model. In reality, total system cost is not the only consideration in deciding the optimal pipeline configuration for distribution grids, but also space optimization. Therefore, in this alternative case, only medium-quality 16 bar pipelines are allowed to prevent the model from installing more than one pipeline between nodes. An exception is made between the electrolyser – HRS – heat demand nodes, where a high-quality 16 bar pipeline is allowed (as this prevents unnecessary purification of H₂ at the HRS) and between the backbone and the nearest heat demand nodes (as this prevents unnecessary installation of a polymeric membrane to meet heat demand).

The pipeline grid of this scenario naturally consists only of 16 bar pipelines and is thus significantly simplified compared to the base case (Figure 12). The conversion technologies were all located at the same locations as for the base case. Nevertheless, some changes were observed in their capacities, compression ranges, or the type of technology that was installed, as shown in Table 24. At the HRS an additional small 16 to 30 bar compressor was required since it was not allowed to install a 30 bar pipeline from the electrolyser. At the backbone, a large medium-quality 16 to 30 bar compressor is installed that is required to feed into the HNS backbone. In the base case, a compressor was located at the LOHC import terminal to feed H₂ into the 4 bar pipeline. In this alternative case, a PSA is required to upgrade the low-quality H₂ supply to medium-quality H₂ that can be accepted into the 16 bar grid.

Figure 12: Grid configuration of base case (above) versus Alternative case 1 (below) where only 16 bar pipelines are installed
*lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

Table 24: Conversion technologies (MW_{H_2} throughput) installed in Alternative case 1 compared to those in the base case.

ID	Compression		Purification	
	Base case	Alternative case 1	Base case	Alternative case 1
*a	51 MW 4-30 bar (lq) 6.6 MW 1-30 bar (mq)	190 MW 16-30 bar (lq)	6.6 MW polymer	
*b	98 MW 1-4 bar (lq)			85 MW PSA
*c	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)	1.9 MW 16-700 bar (hq)		
*d	7.1 MW 8-16 bar (mq)	7.4 MW 8-16 bar (mq)		

The costs associated with the PSA are a significant portion of all conversion and transmission costs for Alternative case 1, yet pipeline and compressor costs are lower than the base case (Figure 13). Furthermore, due to the 85% recovery rate through the PSA located at the LOHC import terminal, less LOHC can supply the 16 bar grid and more liquid H_2 and HNS imports are required, which both have higher marginal costs. Overall, the higher PSA and import costs, outweigh the lower pipeline and compressor costs, leading to a higher total system cost (€265 million) compared to the base case (€250 million).

Figure 13: Left – conversion and transmission costs of base case (blue) versus Alternative case 1 (red); Right – marginal production costs for base case versus Alternative case 1.

4.3.2 Alternative case 2: only medium-quality 8 bar pipelines

In this alternative case, only medium-quality 8 bar pipelines are allowed, with an exception for the pipeline between the electrolyser – HRS – heat demand nodes, where a high-quality 8 bar pipeline is allowed, and between the backbone and the nearby heat nodes, where a low-quality 8 bar pipeline is allowed. This case is very similar to case 1, where only 16 bar pipelines were allowed. The pipeline grid of this case is much simplified compared to the base case as only 8 bar pipelines are installed (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Grid configuration of base case (above) versus Alternative case 2 (below) where only 8 bar pipelines are installed
*lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

Table 25: Conversion technologies (MW_{H_2} throughput) installed in Alternative case 2 compared to those in the base case.

ID	Compression		Purification	
	Base case	Alternative case 2	Base case	Alternative case 2
*a	51 MW 4-30 bar (lq) 6.6 MW 1-30 bar (mq)	185 MW 16-30 bar (lq) 185 MW 8-16 bar (mq)	6.6 MW polymer	
*b	98 MW 1-4 bar (lq)			85 MW PSA
*c	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)	1.9 MW 8-700 bar (hq)		
*d	7.1 MW 8-16 bar (mq)	7.4 MW 8-16 bar (mq)		
*e		45 MW 8-16 bar (mq)		
*f		22 MW 8-16 bar (mq)		
*g		35 MW 8-16 bar (mq)		

The major difference between this case and both the base case and Alternative case 1 is that compressors are now required at all feedstock end-user nodes to comply with their demand pressure (Table 25) leading to much higher compression costs than the former cases. Similar to Alternative case 1, a PSA is installed at the LOHC import terminal to upgrade the H_2 quality to be accepted into the medium-quality 8 bar pipeline. At the backbone, a large 8 to 30 bar compressor is installed such that hydrogen can be fed into the HNS backbone. The total system costs for this scenario are higher (€268 million) than those of the base case (€250 million) or Alternative case 1 (€265 million) (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Left – Marginal costs of production for base case (blue) versus Alternative case 2 (red); Right – costs of conversion and transmission technologies for base case versus Alternative case 2.

The comparison between Alternative case 2 and 1 leads to an important insight: if a simplified pipeline grid is preferred over the complex “optimal” base case scenario, from a cost optimisation point of view, it is preferable to adopt a grid with a pressure high enough to satisfy feedstock demand pressure (or in general the highest demand pressure in the considered area). Nevertheless, the cost difference between Alternative cases 1 and 2 is only marginal (<€3 million), and therefore, the decision for choosing between the grid layout of these two alternative cases could be based on other criteria than the costs alone.

4.3.3 Alternative case 3: only medium-quality 4, 8 and 16 bar pipelines

When given the option to install 4, 8, or 16 bar pipelines, the resulting network layout is similar to Alternative case 1 (section 4.3.1), where only 16 bar pipelines are installed. However, pressure is reduced at three locations to take advantage of 4 and 8 bar pipelines, which have lower CAPEX (Figure 16):

- 4 bar pipelines to serve heat demand near the backbone
- A 4 bar pipeline branching off the 16 bar pipeline from the LOHC terminal
- An 8 bar pipeline to connect the electrolyser supply (via the HRS) to the nearby heat demand

Otherwise, all medium quality 16 bar pipelines are chosen and the difference in total system cost of this scenario compared to Alternative case 1 is minimal and can be attributed to the lower CAPEX from the few lower pressure pipelines (€265.417 and €265.410 million, respectively). Nonetheless, such a result suggests there is little to be gained from mixing 4, 8, and 16 bar pipelines in the same network when compared to one with only 16 bar pipelines.

Figure 16: Grid configuration of base case (above) versus Alternative case 3 (below) where 4, 8, or 16 bar pipelines are installed *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

4.3.4 Alternative case 4: only 16 and 30 bar pipelines

When given the option to only install 16 and 30 bar pipelines, the model opts for two pressure layers: a 30 bar medium-quality pipeline connecting the LOHC import terminal and electrolyser with the backbone and a 16 bar pipeline to connect liquid H₂ imports to the nearest off-takers directly, with additional 16 bar pipelines for connecting the electrolyser to its nearest off-takers other than the HRS (Figure 17,

Table 26). When compared to Alternative case 1, the additional pipelines in this scenario result in

ID	Compression		Purification	
	Base case	Alternative case 4	Base case	Alternative case 4
*a	51 MW 4-30 bar (lq) 6.6 MW 1-30 bar (mq)	12 MW 16-30 bar (mq)	6.55 MW polymer	
*b	98 MW 1-4 bar (lq)			85 MW PSA
*c	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)		
*d	7.1 MW 8-16 bar (mq)	7.4 MW 8-16 bar (mq)		

slightly higher pipeline costs, but these are outweighed by much lower compression costs leading to a lower total system cost overall in this scenario compared to Alternative case 1 (€264.6 and €265.4 million, respectively).

Figure 17: Grid configuration of base case (above) versus Alternative case 4 (below) where only 16 and 30 bar pipelines are installed *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

Table 26: Conversion technologies (MW_{H_2} throughput) installed in Alternative case 4 compared to those in the base case.

ID	Compression		Purification	
	Base case	Alternative case 4	Base case	Alternative case 4
*a	51 MW 4-30 bar (lq) 6.6 MW 1-30 bar (mq)	12 MW 16-30 bar (mq)	6.55 MW polymer	
*b	98 MW 1-4 bar (lq)			85 MW PSA
*c	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)		
*d	7.1 MW 8-16 bar (mq)	7.4 MW 8-16 bar (mq)		

Figure 18 compares the costs of Alternative cases 1 through 4 with those of the base case scenario. It is evident that if the model is forced to choose a simpler grid configuration, one with a 16 and 30 bar (layered) grid results in the lowest total system cost, which is about 6% higher than that of the base case. Of the alternative cases, the 16 and 30 bar grid also results in the lowest conversion and transmission costs (€6.7 million) which is about 12% higher than the base case.

Figure 18: Marginal costs of hydrogen supply (top left); conversion and transmission costs (bottom left); total system costs (right) for Alternative case 1 (only 16 bar), 2 (only 8 bar), 3 (4, 8, and/or 16 bar) and 4 (16 and/or 30 bar) compared to the base case.

4.3.5 Alternative case 5: no imports and biomass gasification

The H2avennet project is used as inspiration for the base case model as this project contains several distinct H₂ suppliers and end-users. However, typical areas for which hydrogen infrastructure will be developed are not likely to contain a biomass gasification plant or H₂ imports other than through the HNS backbone. In this alternative case, the biomass gasification plant, liquid H₂ imports and LOHC imports are removed in order to investigate the effect of these less conventional H₂ supply sources on the overall pipeline configuration (Figure 19, Table 27).

Figure 19: Grid configuration of base case (above) versus Alternative case 5 (below) where biomass and imports are removed from the system *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

Table 27: Conversion technologies (MW_{H_2} throughput) installed in Alternative case 5 compared to those in the base case.

ID	Compression		Purification	
	Base case	Alternative case 5	Base case	Alternative case 5
*a	51 MW 4-30 bar (lq) 6.6 MW 1-30 bar (mq)	12 MW 16-30 bar (mq)	6.55 MW polymer	
*b	98 MW 1-4 bar (lq)			
*c	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)		
*d	7.1 MW 8-16 bar (mq)			
*h		82 MW 1-16 bar (mq)		82 MW polymer

The pipeline configuration of this case is simplified compared to the base case with a few key differences:

- The low-quality 4 bar pipeline is not installed because there is no low-pressure H_2 source (LOHC import).
- A low-quality 30 bar pipeline is installed between the electrolyser and the backbone, though in this case it also branches off to 8 or 16 bar low-quality pipelines to supply the heat demand end-users.
- Despite the lack of medium-quality 16 bar supply from the liquid H_2 terminal, still a medium-quality 16 bar pipeline is installed. Hydrogen from the backbone is purified by polymer membranes at the electrolyser location and subsequently compressed again to feed into the medium-quality 16 bar pipeline that supplies all feedstock end-users.
- There is now a 30 bar low-quality and a 16 bar medium-quality pipeline installed from the location where the biomass plant was previously located (see base case) to the intersection above, where it splits into singular pipelines supplying the feedstock and heat demand. It may seem more intuitive to supply both heat and feedstock nodes with the single 16 bar medium-quality pipeline. However, it would require purification and recompression of backbone hydrogen to be fed into the 16 bar medium-quality network which makes this H_2 stream significantly more expensive than H_2 coming directly from the backbone and therefore the separate 30 bar low-quality pipeline is more cost effective.

The results of this case indicate that having fewer H_2 supply sources of differing pressure and purity characteristics simplifies the overall pipeline configuration. Nevertheless, there are still double pipelines present on certain arcs to satisfy feedstock demand in a cost-efficient way, which demonstrates that feedstock demand characteristics (i.e., pressure and quality) are decisive factors for the pipeline configuration.

4.3.6 Alternative case 6: “typical” decentral hydrogen region scenario

The base case scenario mirrors the H2avennet network, which is a particularly concentrated distribution grid with numerous supply and demand nodes each with specific pressure and quality requirements. In this alternative scenario, the arrangement of the network is kept the same, but distances between nodes are increased by a factor of 2.08 and total volumes are decreased by 49%. Scaling the distances and demand volumes in this way is based on the findings of [60] and is loosely representative of a “typical” decentral hydrogen region. Although certain unique factors to the H2avennet base case scenario will likely not be applicable to future decentral areas (e.g., biomass gasification and large import terminals) these factors were held constant to maintain comparability with the base case. There are striking differences in the pipeline layouts as shown in Figure 20, and the compression and purification technologies as shown in Table 28.

Figure 20: Grid configuration of base case (above) and Alternative case 6 (below) where distances are increased and demand volumes decreased *lq= low quality (98%), mq= medium quality (99.5%), hq = high quality (99.999%).

Table 28: Conversion technologies (MW_{H_2} throughput) installed in Alternative case 6 compared to those in the base case.

ID	Compression		Purification	
	Base case	Alternative case 6	Base case	Alternative case 6
*a	51 MW 4-30 bar (lq) 6.6 MW 1-30 bar (mq)	12 MW 4-30 bar (lq)	6.55 MW polymer	
*b	98 MW 1-4 bar (lq)	32 MW 1-4 bar (lq)		
*c	1.9 MW 30-700 bar (hq)	0.98 MW 30-700 bar (hq)		
*d	7.1 MW 8-16 bar (mq)	7.4 MW 8-16 bar (mq)		
*i		49 MW 16-30 bar (mq)		

Due to the longer distances, the model selects fewer double pipelines between nodes compared to the base case and the overall grid configuration is simpler:

- The 4 bar low-quality pipeline no longer extends to supply heat off-takers on right-hand side of the network with low-cost hydrogen from the LOHC import terminal. Instead, these off-takers are supplied by the electrolyser and a 30 bar medium-quality pipeline that connects the network with the backbone and the liquid H_2 import terminal.
- The 16 bar medium quality network no longer extends directly from the liquid H_2 import terminal all the way to the right-hand side of the network to supply the feedstock off-takers. Instead, these nodes are also supplied by the electrolyser and the 30 bar medium-quality pipeline mentioned above.
- There is no longer purification installed at the backbone as there was in the base case. However, this can likely be attributed to lower demand volumes in this scenario not requiring backbone hydrogen to be purified to supply feedstock off-takers in times of high demand and low electrolyser production.
- There are now only two, rather than three, double pipelines connecting the backbone and liquid H_2 nodes with the heat and feedstock nodes on right-hand side of the network. However, it is notable that even at the longer distances, these two hydrogen streams are still

kept separate with double pipelines to avoid the costs of purification and compression needed to feed low-quality low-pressure hydrogen sources (e.g., LOHC) into a medium-quality 16 bar network.

- There is still a 30 bar high-quality pipeline connecting the electrolyser to the HRS rather than a truck, suggesting that the longer distance between nodes compared to the base case (11 vs 5.3 km) is still not long enough to warrant investment in truck transport.

Based on the observed changes in the optimal grid configuration in this scenario, two key insights are revealed:

First, the simpler grid configuration with fewer double pipelines suggests that at longer distances expected in more dispersed hydrogen regions, it is not always optimal to install multiple pipelines in parallel with one another due to higher CAPEX. In the base case, distances are evidently low enough that multiple pipelines outweigh the cost of additional compression and purification needed for numerous supply and demand nodes with different pressure and purity characteristics to utilise the same pipeline. However, in this scenario, it is suboptimal for certain parts of the network to have a separate designated 4 bar low-quality pipeline for the lower cost LOHC imports as in the base case. Instead, higher pressure medium-quality pipelines are selected to allow for export to the backbone and to satisfy feedstock demand without needing additional compression or purification. It can also be depressurised to serve heat demand. Since future decentral hydrogen regions are likely to have lower demand volumes and longer distances than the H2avennet case, the optimal grid configuration can be expected to look simpler than the base case configuration shown in Figure 20 with fewer overlapping pipelines and a more uniform grid reflecting the characteristics of the higher pressure and purity end-users.

Second, the left-hand side of the network still exhibits some, though fewer, double pipelines to keep medium-quality 16 bar supply from liquid H₂ imports separate from low-quality streams. It also allows the 4 bar low-quality pipeline from the LOHC to supply four heat demand nodes on the left-hand side of the network directly without needing any compression or purification. This suggests that even at longer distances, different purity and pressure requirements from off-takers in future decentral hydrogen regions could result in an optimal solution with multiple pipelines in lieu of investments in purification and compression to achieve a uniform grid. However, these overlapping pressure and purity layers could become less likely if distances were to increase further thus making the relative cost of compression and purification lower compared to pipelines. The optimal grid configuration of future decentral regions will likely be less complex if distances between nodes are greater and if demand characteristics (pressure and purity) are more heterogeneous.

Part C: Future hydrogen grid characteristics

5. Synthesis on main factors and considerations for future hydrogen distribution grid characteristics

This section will focus on interrelating the results from the customer typologies that were determined in Part A with the cost optimization activities in Part B. The hypothetical grid based on the H2avennet project that is used in the model is just one example of a localized grid and cannot account for all the variables that determine the anatomy of a local hydrogen pipeline network. However, by first studying the most prominent potential hydrogen customer typologies (e.g., heat demand in industry or feedstock applications) and incorporating those into the model, the results can serve as a template to represent the DNA of any future regional hydrogen grid that will host an extensive range of demand sinks and supply sources.

5.1 Connecting customer typology insights with optimal distribution grid modelling

The base case modelling results offer insights for optimally connecting end-users with different pressure and quality requirements in the same grid. The model delineates between two types of typical industrial end-users: those using hydrogen for heating applications (low-pressure, low-quality demand) and those using hydrogen for feedstock (medium-pressure, medium-quality demand) or other direct applications such as fuel-cells (high-pressure, high-quality demand).

5.1.1 “Heat” off-takers

The base case results suggest that a designated 4 bar low-quality pipeline is optimal to supply these heat off-takers with low-pressure low-quality hydrogen, largely sourced from the LOHC import terminal. Part A provides some useful insights into what types of customers these generic “heat” off-takers might represent.

As was indicated in Table 5, a wide variety of industrial categories such as food & beverages, textile production, ceramics, glass, metals manufacturing etc. utilize heat for a wide variety of their processes. In the Netherlands, about 40-50% of industrial heat is satisfied with natural gas [65]. If hydrogen is ultimately to replace natural gas for heating demands of industry, then a majority of industrial off-takers with low pressure and quality requirements will be able to directly utilize 4 bar low quality hydrogen pipeline connections¹⁶ as was depicted in Figure 6. A concrete example of such an end-user is the food & beverage industry, which represented 1918 million Nm³ of natural gas demand in 2022 (Table 6). A large majority of this energy demand will be for heat generation utilized in various processes and in different apparatuses such as boilers, industrial drying units and furnaces. Natural gas demand from crop cultivation activities (including greenhouse agriculture) also represents a sizable potential demand (2980 MNm³/yr) which is equivalent to 620 kt/yr of hydrogen and is another example of utilizing hydrogen in industry. It could also represent another potential demand for low/medium/high-quality hydrogen which could be utilized in fuel cells for heat and power production, although this is not explicitly included in the model. Solid Oxide Fuel Cells are specifically

¹⁶ Any additional upgrade in pressure for specific industrial apparatuses will obviously need to be accommodated for within a factory environment.

useful since they can use less pure hydrogen and their high operating temperatures allow for utilization of heat in greenhouses.

5.1.2 “Feedstock” off-takers

The base case results suggest that a designated 16 bar medium-quality pipeline is optimal to supply feedstock demand with 16 bar medium-quality hydrogen, largely sourced from the liquid H₂ import terminal and some from the biomass gasification and electrolyser. Part A provides some useful insights into what types of customers these generic “feedstock” off-takers might represent.

For example, when hydrogen is used as a feedstock in the chemical industry, higher qualities are often desired (>99%) to prevent undesired side reactions. Table 5 also provides examples of certain industrial end-users that require higher pressure streams for various chemical processes such as the Haber Bosch process or hydrogenation in the food and beverage industry. As for the scale of expected feedstock demand, the chemical industry alone constituted the highest demand of natural gas among the customer typologies presented (5448 MNm³/year in 2022 - converted to hydrogen this is equivalent to 1133 kt/year). Therefore, feedstock demand could amount to a significant portion of hydrogen consumption in future distribution grids and the impact such purity and pressure requirements have on grid configurations are important to consider.

5.1.3 Mobility off-takers

Although the potential demand from the domestic transport sector and from dwellings is quite high, for the time being there is still a degree of uncertainty regarding hydrogen uptake in these sectors, which was illustrated by interviews with stakeholders involved in standalone hydrogen areas [1]. Therefore, the modelling activities in Part B consider only a modest demand from a local HRS (which is scaled up as a sensitivity in section 4.2.4) and exclude demand from the built environment in the distribution grid.

When the model was allowed to install 30 bar high-quality pipelines, it always chose to install such a pipeline between the electrolyser and the HRS. However, this was typically not sufficient to satisfy demand at all timesteps. While sufficient H₂ supply from other sources was available during these timesteps, it is not possible to purify such a low H₂ gas stream to fuel cell quality. A polymer membrane is able to handle small quantities of H₂ but cannot reach fuel cell quality, while a PSA can reach fuel cell quality but is not able to handle small quantities of H₂. Therefore, the model was given the option to supply the HRS with alternative truck supply from outside the region. The model did not take possible storage of H₂ from the electrolyser into account, and this may in reality improve the ability to supply the HRS fully with H₂ from the electrolyser. Nevertheless, it is important to realise that connecting a small-scale HRS to a distribution grid is challenging, and local storage or a back-up supply may be necessary.

5.2 Takeaways from modelling

The base case model results clearly indicate that the most optimal grid configuration from a total system cost perspective is one involving multiple pressure and purity layers. This result must be considered carefully in comparison to simpler grid configurations (Alternative cases 1 through 4 – sections 4.3.1 to 4.3.4) which involve only one or two pressure layers and are likely more conventional in practice based on consultation with grid operators. Although the most optimal solution might involve a more complex grid as shown in the base case results (4.1), practical considerations that favour simplicity and more efficient use of space might outweigh the cost savings. Nonetheless, careful analysis of the optimal solution chosen by the model in the base case and scenarios yields important insights to be considered when designing hydrogen distribution grids.

Overall, several important conclusions can be drawn from the model results:

1. If a simplified pipeline configuration is desired, a 30 and 16 bar (layered) grid is optimal.

Alternative cases 1 through 4 force the model to install simpler networks than the base case. An 8 bar network (section 0) results in higher total costs than a 16 bar grid (section 4.3.1) due to the additional compression needed at every feedstock node to increase the hydrogen supply from the 8 bar grid pressure to the 16 bar pressure demanded by the feedstock nodes. When given the option to select 4, 8, or 16 bar pipelines (section 4.3.3), a single 16 bar pressure layer is chosen for the majority of the grid.

Of these four scenarios, Alternative case 4 (section 4.3.4) – with 16 and 30 bar pipelines – results in the lowest total system cost (although it is still 6% higher than the “optimal” solution found in the base case (see Figure 18)). It is evident that installing the additional 30 bar pipelines on top of the 16 bar grid results in lower compression costs than a scenario with only 16 bar pipelines and therefore lower total system costs (however, the difference is minimal (4.3.1) – approximately €800,000). The addition of a 30 bar pipeline allows the electrolyser to export hydrogen to the backbone without unnecessary losses in pressure through a 16 bar network which would then need to be recompressed at the backbone feed-in location.

In future hydrogen regions, a simplified pipeline layout might be preferred over the complex “optimal” base case solution. These results suggest that it is preferable to adopt a grid with a pressure at least high enough to satisfy the highest demand pressure (in this case, at least 16 bar).¹⁷ The results of Alternative cases 1 and 4 suggest that the added pipeline costs of having two separate networks (a 30 bar grid that connects the 30 bar electrolyser supply with the 30 bar backbone “demand” and a 16 bar grid to connect all other demand nodes, which require a maximum of 16 bar) is preferable to selecting a single pressure layer (e.g., 30 or 16 bar) for the entire grid and investing in additional compression and purification. Therefore, future hydrogen areas will need to decide whether the lower total system cost that can be achieved by having a second pressure and/or purity layer outweighs the added complexities of a multi-layered grid.

2. Lower total system costs in base case are driven by lower marginal costs of supply by avoiding losses through a PSA.

Overall, the total system costs for the base case are lower than in Alternative cases 1 through 4, where the model is forced to choose a simpler pipeline configuration. Although the annualised cost of pipelines and compressors is higher in the base case than in the alternative scenarios, it is offset by the costs of the PSA in the alternative scenarios.

Since the simplified scenarios cannot install a designated low-quality pipeline to keep purity levels separate from one another, a large PSA is needed to feed low-quality hydrogen from LOHC imports into the uniform medium-quality grid. The PSA has an 85% recovery rate, which means less LOHC can supply the system, and more is supplied from sources with higher marginal costs (liquid H₂ and HNS imports). These marginal supply costs are the most significant contributor to the higher total system costs observed in the alternative scenarios.

¹⁷ Although mobility demand is technically the highest pressure demanded in the system, it makes up such a small portion of overall demand and is only located at one node that it does not have a strong impact on the overall grid configuration.

The base case scenario reduces marginal costs of supply by injecting the LOHC import into a separate low-quality 4 bar pipeline, thereby avoiding considerable losses through a PSA as seen in the alternative scenarios.

This result leads to a useful insight for future hydrogen regions: using multiple pipeline layers in more-concentrated areas could be a cost-effective strategy to improve system efficiency by avoiding hydrogen recovery losses from utilisation of large-scale PSAs. If future regions have multiple sources of hydrogen with different pressures and purities, investing in separate pipelines could allow low-quality supply to remain separate from higher purity streams and prevent the unnecessary installation of purification technologies with lower recovery rates.

3. The difference in total system costs between the optimal base case configuration and the simpler alternative cases is small. Added complexities will need to be weighed with additional cost savings.

The difference in total system costs of the complex base case scenario and the simpler configuration with only 16 and 30 bar pipelines is minimal (€15 million). With total annualised system costs in the range of €250 million, such cost savings make up a small fraction of the total. Therefore, reducing total system costs should not be the sole decision factor for selecting the optimal distribution grid configuration. Instead, grid operators will need to consider other aspects, such as simplicity of the grid and space availability, when weighing the benefits of reducing total system costs to achieve the most “optimal” grid.

4. Transmission and conversion costs are a small portion of total system costs.

The transmission and conversion costs (i.e., pipelines, trucks, compressors, and purification technologies) of the base case represent only a small portion (€6 million, which amounts to 2.5%) of the total system costs. The majority of the system costs (€244 million) originates from the marginal H₂ production and supply costs. Thus, even though the transmission and conversion costs are lower for the base case compared to those of the alternative cases (the highest costs are for Alternative case 2, €10 million, 3.7%) the effect of these costs is relatively low.

5. Demand nodes are connected to pipelines that most closely match their pressure and quality characteristics.

It is clear from the base case and many of the alternative scenarios that it is optimal for end-users to be connected to a pipeline which most closely matches their required pressure and quality. Due to the differing requirements of heat (1 bar low-quality), feedstock (16 bar medium-quality), and backbone export (30 bar low-quality), three distinct sets of pipelines are often observed to keep these needs separate.

The installation of separate pipelines is likely heavily influenced by the demand nodes of the H2avennet case being so heavily concentrated. Nonetheless, these results provide useful learnings for future concentrated hydrogen regions with various sources and demands for hydrogen: the most optimal grid from a total system cost perspective could be one with separate pressure and purity grids based on end-user requirements. Of course, these cost savings will need to be carefully considered in light of the added complexity of having multiple pipeline layers.

6. Feedstock demand characteristics likely have an outsized impact on pipeline configuration.

Compared to the pressure and quality characteristics of other demand and supply sources, the 16 bar medium-quality demand from feedstock heavily influences the optimal grid configuration. For instance, in Alternative case 5 (section 0), when medium-quality and medium-pressure supply nodes (liquid H₂ and biomass) were removed from the network, a medium-quality 16 bar pipeline was still installed to connect and serve feedstock demand nodes. In this way, a polymeric membrane located at a single location can be used to purify hydrogen from the backbone, pressurise it, and feed it into the 16 bar pipeline. This solution is preferable to installing membranes and compressors separately at each feedstock node.

For future hydrogen regions, this result could be applicable when determining the optimal pressure for a grid serving various feedstock end-users (or other off-takers with higher purity and pressure requirements). It is evident that it is not optimal to select a low-pressure and low-purity distribution grid and install decentralised purification and compression at each demand node. Even when medium-quality and medium-pressure supply sources are removed from the system, the model still selects a 16 bar medium-quality pipeline to connect all feedstock end-users, suggesting that the requirements of many dispersed end-users might have a stronger influence on the optimal grid configuration than dispersed supply sources.

It should be noted that feedstock demand itself does not inherently have an outsized influence on the optimal grid configuration. Rather, since it has a relatively higher pressure and purity requirement than other demand nodes (i.e., heat) and makes up a sizable portion of the total demand in the system, it has a strong influence on the optimal configuration. Accordingly, mobility characteristics do not play a role in distribution grid configuration likely because it is a small fraction of total demand. Overall, future hydrogen regions can expect off-takers with higher pressure and purity requirements than other end-users in the system to have a strong influence on the optimal pressure and purity network, so long as they make up a significant portion of total demand.

7. Different quality requirements from demand nodes can explain some (but not all) double pipeline layers observed in the base case.

Fewer double pipelines are observed between nodes when all end-users require the same level of purity. In the low-quality demand sensitivity (4.2.6), all demand nodes could be served by the same low-quality pipeline. When some end-users require higher purity H₂ than others, the model opts to install separate pipelines to keep low and medium-quality streams separate rather than purifying low-purity supply sources to feed into a medium-quality grid.

However, even when all end-users require the same purity, there are still certain parts of the grid with overlapping pipelines to keep certain pressure levels separate from one another (4, 16, and 30 bar). The different pressure levels allow supply sources to connect with demand nodes of similar pressure requirements without additional investments in compression. The result suggests that it is cost optimal to keep install an additional pipeline rather than choosing a single pressure layer for the entire distribution grid and installing additional compression as needed.

For future regional hydrogen areas, these results indicate that a complex grid with multiple pressure and purity layers could be the most optimal solution when there is a high degree of heterogeneity in end-user characteristics. Accordingly, if end-users have more similar

pressure and purity requirements, the optimal grid configuration can be expected to be less complex and have fewer double pipelines.

8. The optimal grid configuration of future decentral regions will be heavily influenced by the distance between nodes.

The highly concentrated nature of the H2avennet base case evidently has a strong effect on the pipeline configuration. When distances between nodes are approximately doubled in Alternative case 6 (section 4.3.6), fewer overlapping pipelines are observed. Accordingly, in more dispersed hydrogen regions, it will not always be optimal to install multiple pipelines in parallel with one another since the cost of multiple pipelines could exceed that of the additional compression and purification needed for a more uniform grid. In the event that multiple pipelines are not cost optimal and a grid with uniform pressure and purity is desirable, the chosen pressure and purity for the grid will likely reflect the characteristics of the higher pressure and purity end-users (rather than a lower pressure and purity with decentral compression and purification at each end-user location), assuming they make up a sizable part of the total demand, such as feedstock demand as described in sections 4.3.3 and 4.3.6.

However, as seen in part of the network in Alternative case 6, the optimal grid configuration for future hydrogen regions could still involve overlapping pipelines depending on the distance between nodes. The likelihood of such overlapping pipelines is expected to be greater in more concentrated areas with considerable heterogeneity in end-user pressure and purity requirements, which leads to higher costs of compression and purification compared to pipelines.

9. Future regional hydrogen areas will likely be less complex than the H2avennet base case which will result in simpler optimal grid configurations.

It is important to express that the H2avennet case, which served as a rough blueprint to build the fictional base case scenario for the model, is likely more complex than many future regional hydrogen areas are expected to be. The numerous sources of hydrogen supply with differing pressure, quality, and volume characteristics, coupled with a high number of both heat and feedstock industrial off-takers in a heavily concentrated area greatly impact the optimal grid configuration. Thus, it is important to consider how the results of this model can be translated to learnings for future regional areas with simpler configurations.

For example, if future hydrogen regions have fewer supply nodes of differing pressures and purities, the optimal network will be less likely to exhibit as many overlapping pipelines as seen in the base case results. For instance, Alternative case 5 (section 0) excludes imports and biomass gasification and the optimal grid configuration is a simplified pipeline network with no 4 bar grid and fewer overlapping pipelines. Furthermore, if future regional hydrogen areas have only industrial heat off-takers and lack medium-quality feedstock demand, the network can also be expected to be much simpler since overlapping pipelines would not be needed to keep higher-purity hydrogen streams separate from low-quality streams (section 4.2.6).

Finally, if future hydrogen regions serve higher portions of mobility demand compared to industry, higher pressure and purity pipelines could be seen (e.g., more 30 bar high-quality pipelines). Although the higher mobility demand sensitivity tested the impact of a ten-fold increase in mobility demand (section 4.2.4), the relative portion of mobility demand

compared to total industrial demand was still quite low. Mobility demand presents a unique challenge for distribution grids with low or medium-quality hydrogen supply sources since purification options are limited (see 5.1.3).

If future hydrogen regions develop largely to meet decentral mobility demand and there is sufficient electrolyser capacity and/or enough demand to warrant a PSA, the socially optimal grid might look more similar to characteristics favouring mobility off-takers (higher pressures and purities), as the results of this model clearly indicate that characteristics of off-takers with higher-pressure and purity requirements weigh heavily in the determination of the most optimal configuration (e.g., Alternative case 3 (section 4.3.3) when given the option to install either 4, 8, or 16 bar pipelines, the model opts for the highest pressure option despite it having higher CAPEX than 4 or 8 bar in order to satisfy feedstock demand and prevent dispersed compression and purification at each feedstock node, while still allowing other lower pressure and purity demand nodes to be served by the same grid).

6. Conclusions

The results of Part A indicate that there is significant potential hydrogen demand in the Netherlands based on present demand for natural gas in relevant sectors (~1095 PJ natural gas per year; ~8 million tons H₂ equivalent per year), which some portion can be expected to convert to hydrogen in the future. While hydrogen end-users vary in the specifics of their pressure, purity, and volume requirements, two prominent customer typologies emerge as likely industrial end-users of hydrogen: those using hydrogen in industrial heat applications and those using hydrogen for feedstock.

These customer typologies were modelled in an example distribution grid based on the H2avennet project to determine the optimal grid configuration from a total system cost perspective given varying sources and demands for hydrogen, each with specific pressure and purity characteristics, in a concentrated network. The results suggest that if there is a large diversity of suppliers and off-takers, the most optimal solution is likely one that involves multiple overlapping pressure and purity layers, with some pipelines running in parallel with one another.

Sensitivity analyses reinforce the robustness of the model, as minimal changes in the overall grid configuration were observed when cost and technical parameters were adjusted. The alternative scenarios make clear that the most optimal grid configuration is heavily impacted by the type of demand (pressure and purity requirements) and the distance between nodes. In general, the results suggest that the most optimal grid configuration will become less complex at longer distances and when end-user demand characteristics are more homogeneous. Future work should continue with modelling different types of regional hydrogen distribution grids, as more is learned about their expected size and makeup.

Overall, the total system costs of the model's most optimal grid configuration should be compared to those of more simplistic cases where the model was forced to choose fewer pipelines. While costs are higher for the simpler configurations, grid operators will need to carefully consider whether the expected savings outweigh the added complexities associated with a multi-layered network when assessing the most desirable configuration for future hydrogen distribution grids.

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Appendix I: Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
CAPEX	Capital expenditures
CBS	Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek
CHP	Combined heat and power
CPU	Central processing unit
DSO	Distribution System Operator
ETS	Emissions trading system
FCEV	Fuel cell electric vehicles
GTS	Gasunie Transport Services
HNS	HyNetwork Services
Hq	High quality = 99.999%
HRS	Hydrogen refuelling station
IEA	International Energy Agency
ISO TC	International Organization for Standardization Technical Committee
kWh	Kilowatt-hour
kWh _e	Kilowatt-hour electric
kWh _{H₂}	Kilowatt-hour hydrogen
LH ₂	Liquified hydrogen
LHV	Lower heating value
LOHC	Liquid organic hydrogen carrier
Lq	Low quality = 98%
MILP	Mixed-integer linear programming
MIP	Mixed-integer problem
MJ	Megajoule
Mq	Medium quality = 99.5%
MW	Megawatt
MW _e	Megawatt electric
MW _{H₂}	Megawatt hydrogen
NG	Natural gas
NL	The Netherlands
NTP	Normal temperature and pressure
O&M	Operations and maintenance
OPEX	Operating expenditures
PJ	Petajoule
PSA	Pressure swing adsorption
RAM	Random access memory
RINS	Relaxation induced neighbourhood search
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
THT	Tetrahydrothiophene